

Validation of the typology and classification system in Bulgaria for assessment the ecological status of surface water bodies of categories “river”, “lake” and “transitional waters”

Final Report

Annex 4

Methods for the analysis of BQEs, reference conditions and the ecological status classification system in the target types of surface waters

MACROPHYTES

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1 Introduction and objectives according to the ToR

Macrophytes are one of the biological quality elements (BQE) required for the classification of ecological status and ecological potential of surface water bodies under the European Water Framework Directive (WFD). It is relevant for lakes/reservoirs and rivers.

National methods for ecological status classification have been developed for all national river and lake types designated in Bulgaria (Gecheva et al., 2013, Regulation N-4 from 14.09.2012 towards characterising surface waters, national Ordinance from 2012 [MoEW 2012]).

For some river types (R4, R7, R8, R14) and for the lake type L5, the Bulgarian methods were successfully intercalibrated with methods from other EU member states (MS), which share the comparable types. The results of the intercalibration are summarised in the reports of Birk et al. (2013), Pall et al. (2016a, 2016b, 2018) and officially published in the EU Decisions 2013/480/EC (2013) and 2018/229/EC (2018).

Activity 6.3 of the ToR requires the validation of the classification system for the assessment of the ecological status of river and lake types that have not yet been included in the intercalibration.

This task includes:

- 1) An evaluation of existing classification methods and types to be considered
- 2) An evaluation of available data on macrophytes and relevant pressures
- 3) Calculations of pressure-response relationships
- 4) A definition of reference conditions and reference values for the relevant metric
- 5) Setting of class boundaries

Activity 6.4 of the ToR requires the development of a classification system for the assessment of the ecological potential of heavily modified water bodies of rivers, lakes/reservoirs and transitional waters under the approach adopted by WG ECOSTAT and Water directors (integrated requirements of both CIS WFD approach and Prague approach of "mitigating measures").

2 Available Data on Macrophytes and Pressures

2.1 Monitoring sites

The consolidated data set includes data from 218 monitoring sites belonging to 175 “Surface Water Bodies” (SWB) of lakes and rivers (with up to 3 sites per SWB), sampled between January and November 2020.

For lakes, 79 sites were examined with up to nine transects. The sites represent 19 lake types including 4 Types of Black Sea coastal lakes (L07 – L10). From the examined 79 sites, 35 lakes were found to have no or just few macrophyte population (abundance [ABD] <21), which did not allow any assessment or calculation of the “Ecological Quality Ratio” (EQR), respectively. As this was essential for further analysis these lakes therefore were excluded from the data set. The remaining data set for further validation was quite small with just 42 lakes.

For rivers, 139 sites were sampled, but 7 sites were found to have dried out and without macrophytes. The remaining 132 sites were assigned to 14 types, including 9 sites in the transitional Black Sea river firths (R16). From these data set, sites were excluded that had no or insufficient abundance data for the EQR to be calculated, which led to a remaining data set of 88 river sites, with three of missing typology, resulting in 85 river sites.

The following tables show the number of remaining monitoring sites for lakes and rivers per type, category and altitude class (Table 1 to Table 5).

Table 1. Number of monitoring sites available per lake type and category (AWB: Artificial water body, HMWB: Heavily modified water body).

Type	AWB	HMWB	Natural
L01			1
L02			3
L03		2	
L04	1	1	2
L05a			2
L06	1		2
L07			3
L08		2	3
L09		1	
L10			
L11 (L11c)			1
L12			4
L13		3	
L14			3
L15	1	2	
L16		2	1
L17		1	
sum	3	14	25

Table 2. Number of monitoring sites available per river type and category (TR: Transitional water body, HMWB: Heavily modified water body, Natural: Natural water body).

Type	TR	HMWB	Natural
R01			4
R03		2	4
R04		5	
R05a		3	6
R07		5	
R08		4	
R09		2	5
R10		2	4
R11		4	7
R12		4	5
R13		1	6
R14			
R15			5
R16	7		
sum	7	32	46

Table 3. Number of monitoring sites available per lake type and altitude class (in m above sea level).

Type	<200	200-500	500-800	800-1800	>1800
L01					1
L02		1	2		
L03				2	
L04		1	2	1	
L05a	2				
L06	2		1		
L07	3				
L08	5				
L09	1				
L10					
L11 (L11c)				1	
L12		4			
L13		3			
L14	3				
L15	3				
L16	3				
L17	1				
sum	23	9	5	4	1

Table 4. Number of monitoring sites available per river type and altitude class (in m above sea level).

Type	<200	200-500	500-800	800-1800	>1800
R01		1		3	
R03		2	2	2	
R04	3	1	1		
R05a	3	3	2	1	
R07	5				
R08	4				
R09	3	4			
R10	6				
R11	11				
R12	9				
R13	3	2	1	1	
R14					
R15	4		1		
R16	7				
sum	58	13	7	7	0

Table 5. Number of monitoring sites available per lake type and surface area class.

Type	<0.5 km ²	0.5-1 km ²	1-10 km ²	10-100 km ²	no data
L01	1				
L02		1		2	
L03			1	1	
L04		2		2	
L05a					2
L06	2	1			
L07	1		1	1	
L08	1		2	2	
L09	1				
L10					
L11 (L11c)			1		
L12		2		2	
L13				3	
L14			1	2	
L15			1	2	
L16	1	2			
L17	1				
sum	8	8	7	17	2

2.2 Biological data

Mapping of macrophytes in rivers and lakes was carried out according to the official Bulgarian WFD-methods (Regulation N-4 from 14.09.2012 towards characterising surface waters; Gecheva et al., 2013).

The national macrophyte-based method – Reference Index Bulgaria (RI-BG; Gecheva et al., 2013) is established for assessment of ecological status of rivers and lakes in Bulgaria. It is compliant with European standardisation legislation (EN 14184: 2014, EN 14996: 2006, EN 15460, CEN 230165). The evaluation and the calculation procedures meet the requirements of the Water Framework Directive (WFD) and are in line with the recommendations of the implementation groups CIS Working Group 2.3 and 2.A (REFCOND, ECOSTAT).

Overview method for rivers

The macrophyte survey is carried out once during the main vegetation period (May until end of June).

Sampling usually is done using rubber boots or wading trousers, by hand or with a rake. In bigger rivers sampling can be done by boat, using a water viewer (aqua-scope) in combination with a double-sided rake connected to a rope.

In each sampling site usually a 100 m long section is surveyed. The abundances of all single species are registered using a five-level scale.

All submerged growing species as well as those with floating leaves and amphiphytic taxa are taken into account if they are submerged or floating.

The taxonomic composition of aquatic macrophytes (stoneworts, mosses and vascular plants) is assessed on a species level, except for Chara, Chiloscyphus and Sphagnum, which are determined on genus level.

Overview method for lakes:

The macrophyte survey is carried out once during the main vegetation period (end of June until September).

Sampling can be done by boat, using a water viewer (aqua-scope) in combination with a double-sided rake connected to a rope.

In each sampling site a belt-transect of 20–30 m width orthogonal to the shoreline and positioned within an ecologically homogenous section of the littoral is surveyed. The transect number is in correlation to the lake size.

At each transect four different depth zones are sampled (0–1 m, 1–2 m, 2–4 m and >4 m). The abundances of all single species in all depth zones are registered using a five-level scale.

All submerged growing species as well as those with floating leaves and amphiphytic taxa are taken into account if they are submerged or floating.

The taxonomic composition of aquatic macrophytes (stoneworts, mosses and vascular plants) is assessed on a species level, except for Chara and Sphagnum, which are determined on genus level.

2.3 Biological metrics

The biological metric used is the “Reference Index-BG” (RI-BG) (Gecheva et al., 2013) as this method is the official one, used for WFD-compliant macrophyte-based assessment of rivers and lakes in Bulgaria (National Ordinance from 2012 [MoEW 2012]). This method is already intercalibrated for some lake and river types. Furthermore, the principal approach of the Reference Index – with country-specific adaptations – is widely used in Europe. Hence it was abstained from testing additionally other macrophyte-based metrics.

2.4 Physical-chemical data

In addition to the biological data, physical-chemical data (Table 6) are available from most sampling dates or from sampling dates close to the date of biological sampling. The data included general physical-chemical parameters such as water temperature, electric conductivity, oxygen concentration and saturation, pH, phosphorus and compounds (total phosphorus, orthophosphate [as soluble reactive phosphorus]), nitrogen and compounds (total nitrogen, ammonium, nitrate, nitrite), and biological oxygen demand BOD₅.

Table 6. List of available physical-chemical parameters (abbreviation in brackets) for lakes and rivers and the total number of samples from the campaign 2020.

Parameter	Lakes (n=42)	Rivers (n=88)
Elevation	42	88
Water temperature (WT)	42	88
pH	41	88
Electric conductivity (EC)	41	88
Dissolved oxygen (O ₂)	41	82
Oxygen saturation (O ₂ -sat)	41	82
Salinity	42	88
Transparency	30	15
Biological oxygen demand (BOD ₅)	37	88
Total nitrogen (TN)	42	88
Ammonium-nitrogen (NH ₄ -N)	42	88
Nitrite-nitrogen (NO ₂ -N)	42	88
Nitrate-nitrogen (NO ₃ -N)	42	88
Orthophosphate-P = soluble reactive P (SRP)	42	88
Total phosphorus (TP)	42	88

2.5 Hydro-morphological Pressures

The pressures used from lakes and rivers for the evaluation of the pressure – response relationships are displayed in Table 7. In the following pressure – response relationships were tested for both, single metrics and the sum of all pressures and weighted combinations of different pressures.

Table 7. List of used hydro-morphological pressures for lakes and rivers at the sampling site (in brackets: abbreviations as given in the raw data and used below).

Pressure-Parameter	Lakes	Rivers
Impoundment	+	
Migration_Barriers	+	+
Hydropeaking	+	
Abstraction	+	
Dams_segment	+	
Lateral dams at the sampling site (Dams_site)	+	
Temperature Modification	+	+
Channelisation	+	
Alteration of riparian vegetation at the segment (VegRiparian_seg)	+	+
Alteration of riparian vegetation at the sampling site (VegRiparian_site)	+	+
Habitat alteration at the segment (HabAlter_seg)	+	+
Habitat alteration at the sampling site (HabAlter_site)	+	+
Toxic impact (Toxic)	+	+
Water level fluctuations (Water_level_fluct)		+
Aquaculture		+
Invasive species		+
Anthropogenic pressure - landscape		
Anthropogenic pressure - physical chemical		

2.6 Corine Landcover

Data from the Corine Landcover were used for each survey site, with a selected buffer around the site and clipped to the catchment area of the river and lake, to reduce the input data and to represent the regional influents of the landcover to the survey site.

3 Statistical methods

3.1 Analysis of lake- and river-type-classification based on species abundances

In order to verify the proposed lake- and river-type grouping and to identify potential stressors and effects by other environmental influences that promote grouping of macrophytes, a non-metric multidimensional scaling (nMDS) was performed in R, based on macrophyte abundances per site and Bray-Curtis similarity (R Core Team, 2021). Species and environmental variables that had a significant correlation to the nMDS were fitted to the plot with vectors ($P \leq 0.05$ based on 999 permutations). Results of the nMDS ordination were grouped by (1) the different proposed groupings as given, (2) by water body type (WBType) to manually identify potential groupings of Sites and Types and (3) by the newly identified Groups. These results were verified for differences between groups using a permutational analysis of variance based on Bray-Curtis similarities (PERMANOVA, R-package *vegan*; Anderson, 2001). To compare species abundances based on environmental grouping, an ANOSIM-Test was also performed. A multilevel pattern analysis of the library *indicspecies* was used to find the species that were significantly abundant for a particular habitat grouping parameter, which is not directly indicated by the NMDS, giving potential indicator species to identify lake- or river groups.

3.2 Analysis of pressures and environmental data for correlation with EQR

The provided data set was merged based on site codes and reduced to sites for which the EQR had been rechecked and verified. Measurement parameters obtained in classes, e.g., Flow velocity (slow, fast, ...), were transformed to numeric values to allow a correlation analysis with the numeric EQR value. A correlation matrix was calculated in Microsoft Excel resulting in R-values giving information of positive and negative correlation of environmental parameters to the EQR of the respective site. Further analysis was performed in R (R Core Team, 2021). Chemical water parameters were partly log-transformed to fulfil normal distribution. After this, a linear regression model was calculated for each parameter assessed to be compared with the EQR value over all sites, and plotted into a graph for data inspection. The output linear model was then used to extract p-values and model indices for each parameter, which verified the Excel data set. A linear mixed model was used to calculate the differences of intercepts or offsets from the correlation of a defined pressure index (PI) and the EQR values for each site using the package *lme4* (Bates et al, 2012, 2015).

3.3 Tools and libraries

Statistical analysis was done using R in RStudio (R Core Team, 2020; RStudio Team, 2020). For data handling and visual processing, the following additional packages were used: *Openxlsx* for reading, writing, and editing .xlsx files; *reshape2* to transform data; *devtools* for installing external toolboxes; *tidyverse* to clean and handle data sets, *vegan* to run and plot the NMDS along other methods, e.g., the ANOSIM-test (Oksanen et al. 2020); *indicspecies* for multilevel pattern analysis; *lme4* for linear mixed model calculations; *ggplot2* in addition with *ggpubr*, *svglite*, *gridExtra*, *egg* and *grid* to create data visualisations.

4 Rivers

4.1 Descriptive analyses of the biological community

4.1.1 General physio-chemical parameters

In order to get a first rough characteristic overview of the Bulgarian river study sites assessed, the key elevation and chemo-physical measurements taken at each study site were displayed for each Water Body Type (WBType, Figure 1). Here, multiple conclusions can be drawn regarding potential grouping and community characteristics for aquatic macrophytes.

The river types R01 and R03 were clearly assigned to mountainous and semi-mountainous rivers, but also in R05, R13 and R15 there were some rivers sampled that were at higher elevations than the rest of the sites within the proposed WBTypes. This obviously can lead to difficulties at the further progress of classification, as potential outliers of elevation-adapted macrophytes could affect the grouping process. The spread of water temperature within the WBTypes mostly showed a relation to the site's elevation, but R08, R10 and R14 had opposite correlation, driven by potential pressures (Table 9). The rivers of Type R13 had the largest amplitude from 12 up to 27.5°C. The pH value was found to be highest in R01 and R16, with most of the other types ranging means between pH 7.5 and pH 8.2. Electric conductivity was lowest in R01, followed by R03. The highest values were found in the transitional rivers R16. Dissolved oxygen had mean values of mostly 7-9 mg/L, with R01 with the highest mean value and R16 with the highest over-all value. The lowest value of 0 mg/L was found in R07. These values are supported by the measurements of oxygen saturation, where especially R16 showed high super saturation of up to 175%. A WBType-based correlation of water temperature and dissolved oxygen did not show the common pattern of temperature-driven oxygen levels, which was also verified by the overall-test, where this relationship was not found to be significantly correlated (Table 8, Table 10). A level of salinity was present in just few rivers of R05, R12, R13 and R14 that had minor values. However, in R16 high salinity was measured due to the influence of marsh and sea water. Transparency was not measured at many rivers due to shallow conditions. The rivers of the lowland showed rather low transparency. The range of biochemical oxygen demand (BOD₅) was heterogenous between river types, depending on the available habitat and type of water body with no further explaining pattern. Total nitrogen was higher in the rivers of the lowland, compared to rivers of the semi-mountainous region. This was also relevant with all other indicators for nutrients, such as ammonium (NH₄N), nitrite (NO₂N), nitrate (NO₃N, orthophosphate (SRP), and total phosphorus (TP). Here, outliers with higher values measured can be observed in the rivers R03-R05, but R01 always had lowest concentrations.

To proof the interlinked relationships of the key environmental parameters, an over-all correlation analysis was processed (Table 8). In this analysis, the assignments of WBTypes were not considered such as given in the example of Table 9 and Table 10.

Figure 1: Boxplots of characteristic and chemical-physical parameters of all study sites assessed.

Table 8: Selected significant correlations of the key environmental parameters assessed in all river sites.

Param1	Param2	cor	p	*	Param1	Param2	cor	p	*
BOD_log	TN_log	0,4	< 0,001	***	O2_sat_log	BOD_log	-0,44	< 0,001	***
BOD_log	NH4N_log	0,6	< 0,001	***	O2_sat_log	NH4N_log	-0,25	0,006	**
BOD_log	NO2N_log	0,5	< 0,001	***	O2_sat_log	NO2N_log	-0,21	0,023	*
BOD_log	SRP_log	0,4	< 0,001	***	O2_sat_log	SRP_log	-0,17	0,06	.
BOD_log	TP_log	0,4	< 0,001	***	O2_sat_log	TP_log	-0,15	0,097	.
BOD_log	ElevCalc	-0	0,006	**	pH	Sal	0,43	< 0,001	***
EC_log	BOD_log	0,4	< 0,001	***	pH	Trans	0,68	< 0,001	***
EC_log	TN_log	0,5	< 0,001	***	pH	EC_log	0,21	0,015	*
EC_log	NH4N_log	0,4	< 0,001	***	pH	O2_log	0,31	< 0,001	***
EC_log	NO2N_log	0,3	< 0,001	***	pH	O2_sat_log	0,31	< 0,001	***
EC_log	NO3N_log	0,3	< 0,001	***	pH	TN_log	-0,16	0,066	.
EC_log	SRP_log	0,3	0,003	**	Sal	Trans	0,46	0,014	*
EC_log	TP_log	0,5	< 0,001	***	Sal	EC_log	0,6	< 0,001	***
NH4N_log	NO2N_log	0,5	< 0,001	***	Sal	BOD_log	0,16	0,071	.
NH4N_log	SRP_log	0,5	< 0,001	***	Sal	NO3N_log	-0,18	0,042	*
NH4N_log	TP_log	0,5	< 0,001	***	Sal	ElevCalc	-0,16	0,07	.
NH4N_log	ElevCalc	-0	0,032	*	SRP_log	ElevCalc	-0,24	0,006	**
NO2N_log	NO3N_log	0,4	< 0,001	***	TN_log	NH4N_log	0,43	< 0,001	***
NO2N_log	SRP_log	0,5	< 0,001	***	TN_log	NO2N_log	0,52	< 0,001	***
NO2N_log	TP_log	0,6	< 0,001	***	TN_log	SRP_log	0,58	< 0,001	***
NO2N_log	ElevCalc	-0	0,003	**	TN_log	ElevCalc	-0,49	< 0,001	***
NO3N_log	SRP_log	0,4	< 0,001	***	TP_log	ElevCalc	-0,43	< 0,001	***
NO3N_log	TP_log	0,5	< 0,001	***	Trans	EC_log	0,62	< 0,001	***
NO3N_log	ElevCalc	-0	< 0,001	***	Trans	ElevCalc	-0,44	0,029	*
O2_log	BOD_log	-1	< 0,001	***	WT	Sal	0,38	< 0,001	***
O2_log	TN_log	-0	0,062	.	WT	Trans	0,67	< 0,001	***
O2_log	NH4N_log	-0	0,003	**	WT	EC_log	0,52	< 0,001	***
O2_log	NO2N_log	-0	0,002	**	WT	NO2N_log	0,19	0,032	*
O2_log	SRP_log	-0	0,026	*	WT	TP_log	0,36	< 0,001	***
O2_log	TP_log	-0	0,017	*	WT	ElevCalc	-0,54	< 0,001	***

Table 9: Correlation of water temperature and elevation for each WBType (rivers).

WBType	R
R01	-0.48
R03	-0.53
R04	-0.24
R05	-0.6
R07	-0.84
R08	0.44
R09	-0.73
R10	0.17
R11	-0.32
R12	-0.66
R13	-0.7
R14	0.03
R15	-0.66
R16	-0.16

Table 10: Correlation of water temperature and dissolved oxygen (log) for each WBType (rivers).

WBType	R
R01	0,13
R03	-0,1
R04	0,54
R05	-0,12
R07	NA
R08	0,11
R09	NA
R10	-0,7
R11	0,27
R12	-0,12
R13	NA
R14	0,18
R15	-0,47
R16	0,22

4.1.2 Analysis of proposed River type grouping

A similarity analyses using non-metric multidimensional scaling (nMDS) was carried out to represent the species communities in a proper way of scaling, based on the macrophyte abundances for each site. The potential groupings of species community were analysed in terms of river types and altitude classes. The nMDS based on macrophyte abundance per site, grouped for WBTypes, revealed no clear clustering to different groups (Figure 2). Just the rivers of the mountain ranges seem to fit to the left side of the plot, where R04 and R03 show some outliers to the opposite site that do not fit to the overall grouping (R03: BG3TU00723MS0171 and R04: BG1IS04229MS1290). The grouping of WBTypes to the corresponding altitude classes resulted in a well separated pattern displaying an elevational gradient from left to right (the two outliers removed, Figure 3). The macrophyte communities of river sites belonging to the altitude class 500-800m show a wider spread, which can be addressed to a potential heterogenous climate in this altitude range, compared to the other groups. Species grouping therefore seems to be more complex and may be more dependent on a mix of different factors, where the change of macrophyte communities with elevation rather is a side effect with a smooth transition.

Figure 2: nMDS plot of species abundances of Bulgarian rivers, grouped by WBTypes.

Figure 3: nMDS plot of species abundances, grouped by altitude class.

Originally, the Bulgarian macrophyte-based assessment system was specified for three main groups of river types, further called “original main grouping”: (types not represented in the dataset due to missing or too few observations are coloured in grey)

- Mountainous and semi-mountainous rivers
 - R1
 - R2, R3
 - R4, R5
- Rivers influenced by subterranean ground water (R9, R15)
- Rivers of the plains
 - R7, R8, R12, R13
 - R10, R11, R16
 - R14

The similarity analyses using non-metric multidimensional scaling (nMDS) was performed based on macrophyte abundance data of each monitoring site as provided in the data set, that was assigned to a valid EQR code for further homogeneity of data handling. The analysis performed here confirms the grouping of types as displayed above for the quality element macrophytes. As result of the nMDS analysis three major groups of river types can be differentiated (Figure 4): There is some overlap found between groups, but each group builds a unique pattern of species community and therefore displays a valid realistic approach of grouping of river types to simplify mapping of these river systems.

Figure 4: nMDS of groups assigned by the recent typology based on macrophyte species composition (abundance data).

In addition to the original proposal with main groups, the existing detailed grouping of river types as given in the II Intermediate Report: Results of the Field sampling was tested for validity (Dicon, Uba, Deltares, 2020). Here, just R16 was moved to a single group, compared to the grouping as applied above. The analysis is based on the single sub-groups provided below and is further called “original detailed grouping” (types not represented due to missing data coloured in grey).

- Mountainous and semi-mountainous rivers
 - R1
 - R2, R3
 - R4, R5
- Rivers influenced by subterranean ground water (R9, R15)
- Rivers of the plains
 - R7, R8, R12, R13
 - R10, R11
 - R14
- Transitional rivers
 - R16

As described above, also an nMDS-plot was processed to visualize and test for a differentiation of groups provided (Figure 5). The mountainous rivers R01 and R03 clearly separate from the other grouping, whereby the rest of the groups show overlaps in different pattern and size. R05 could be separated from other groups, but R04 has a larger spread in another field of species communities. The group of

the groundwater influenced rivers R09 and R15 is two-tailed where R09 has a small spread and is almost separated from other groups, but R15 has a large spread and therefore leads to more overlap with other groups.

Figure 5: nMDS of groups assigned by the original typology.

The groups were analysed for statistical validity. Compared to (1) the single groups of WBTypes, (2) the groups suggested with the original main grouping and (3) the groups by altitude class, the original detailed typology as given in the II Intermediate Report (Dicon, UBA, Deltares, 2020) did reveal better grouping results in ANOSIM-Test as displayed in Table 15, regarding the verification of the typology. Furthermore, the original detailed grouping with a total of 8 groups did fit better than the original main grouping. Although all groupings state a significant fit of the species abundances to the groups, the R value, the metric for the fit of the species abundance to the groups, is higher for the detailed assignment, compared to main grouping. The groupings further also show a good differentiation when analysed for differences between groups using the PERMANOVA analysis, with a comparable good R score and high significant difference (Table 11, Table 12). Finally, the pairwise factorfit is a detailed test for differences between each group, revealing a clear distinction of each group in the main grouping and almost all groups in the detailed grouping, which can be addressed to low sampling size for the sub-groups (Table 13, Table 14).

The comparison of ANOSIM tests show that, regarding typological grouping approaches, the original detailed version fits best (Table 15). The elevational aspect seems to explain a lot of sites, but other effects such as salinity, ground water influence and morphological characteristics need to be taken into account. To summarize the grouping process of typology, we can confirm the detailed typology as best explaining grouping version for river typology.

Table 11: PERMANOVA of the original main grouping to test for differences between groups.

PERMANOVA: Test for differences between groups

adonis2(formula = mak ~ Group, permutations = 999, method = "bray")					
	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	Pr(>F)
Group	2	2.6881	0.08623	3.8693	0.001 ***
Residual	82	28.4840	0.91377		
Total	84	31.1721	1.00000		

Table 12: PERMANOVA of the original detailed grouping by the intermediate report to test for differences between groups.

PERMANOVA: Test for differences between groups

adonis2(formula = mak ~ Group, permutations = 999, method = "bray")					
	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	Pr(>F)
Group	6	6.7787	0.21746	3.6126	0.001 ***
Residual	78	24.3933	0.78254		
Total	84	31.1721	1.00000		

Table 13: Pairwise factorfit of original main grouping to detect distinct differences between each group assigned.

Pairwise factorfit – Distinct differences between each group (in p-values)

	1_R01-R05	2_R09+R15
2_R09+R15	0.0140	-
3_R07-R16	0.0015	0.0015

Table 14: Pairwise factorfit of the original detailed grouping by the intermediate report to detect distinct differences between each group assigned.

Pairwise factorfit – Distinct differences between each group (in p-values)

	1_R01	2_R02,R03	3_R04,R05	4_R07,R08,R12,R13	5_R09,R15	7_R10,R11
2_R02,R03	0.0184	-	-	-	-	-
3_R04,R05	0.0052	0.0057	-	-	-	-
4_R07,R08,R12,R13	0.0052	0.0052	0.0852	-	-	-
5_R09,R15	0.0052	0.0105	0.0105	0.0052	-	-
7_R10,R11	0.0052	0.0052	0.0112	0.2564	0.0105	-
8_R16	0.0057	0.0057	0.3190	0.2709	0.0052	0.0185

Table 15: ANOSIM Test for fit of abundance data to the assigned groups.

Group	ANOSIM R	Significance (p)
WBTypes	0.4486	0.001
Groups given by the original main grouping	0.276	0.001
Groups given by the original detailed typology	0.3104	0.001
Altitude class	0.3842	0.001

Next, the species that significantly interacted to the distance matrix were displayed in the plot to get further information about potential species communities for each river type group assigned (Figure 6). Here, a pattern of species known to be found at rivers with specific characteristics gives a first overview of macrophyte communities in the Bulgarian rivers. To get further information about distinct macrophytes that can be used as indicator species for a main group (original main grouping) or a subgroup (original detailed grouping by the intermediate report), a multilevel pattern analysis resulted in a remarkable clear differentiation, that can be used for quickly mapping and classifying Bulgarian rivers in the future (Table 16, Table 17).

Figure 6: nMDS plot of species abundances of Bulgarian rivers, displaying all species with significant interaction to the distance matrix, grouped by WBTypes.

The tables provided (Table 16, Table 17) give two options for potential further mapping:

1. Use the main grouping approach to get a rough overview of a typological group for a river (Figure 5). Even though the PERMANOVA revealed statistically poor differences between groups (Table 11), and the ANOSIM R was lower, compared to other variants, there are multiple species found with a significant abundance to one specific group. These species can be used as general indicators and further sub-grouping, if needed.
2. Use the detailed grouping approach as given in the intermediate report. Here, by more and smaller groups, a fine separation is possible, but with the lack of indicator organism for each specific group, due to the high complexity (Table 17). As a positive effect, this level of detail displays more combinations of species, and therefore gives information about single species that are found in multiple groups. It also gives further information about the connection to potential pressures or typologies (see next chapter).

In summary, the provided and verified river typology is a multitool for further research and enables quick and reliable assignment of rivers to a specific group (or subgroup).

Table 16: Significant species interaction to each group assigned, stating potential indicator species for the original main grouping.

Group	Species	stat	p.value	signif.	
1	Mentha longifolia	0.424	0.0025	**	1_R01-R05
	Petasites hybridus	0.326	0.0087	**	
	Polygonum lapathifolium	0.317	0.0215	*	
	Juncus effusus	0.279	0.0499	*	
2	Berula erecta	0.577	0.0001	***	2_R09+R15
	Rumex sp.	0.551	0.0001	***	
	Myosoton aquaticum	0.484	0.0003	***	
	Catabrosa aquatica	0.472	0.0011	***	
	Juncus sp.	0.339	0.0188	*	
	Ranunculus repens	0.332	0.0244	*	
3	Potamogeton pectinatus	0.336	0.0195	*	3_R07-R16
	Ceratophyllum demersum	0.331	0.0339	*	
2+3	Sparganium erectum	0.329	0.0355	*	2_R09+R15 + 3_R07-R16
	Lemna minor	0.309	0.0465	*	
	Typha latifolia	0.314	0.0415	*	

Table 17: Significant species interaction to each group assigned, stating potential indicator species for the original detailed grouping by the intermediate report.

Group	Species	stat	p.value	signif.	Detail
1	<i>Mentha spicata</i>	0.527	0.0106	*	1_R01
	<i>Marchantia polymorpha</i>	0.471	0.0452	*	
	<i>Equisetum telmateia</i>	0.471	0.0479	*	
2	<i>Platyhypnidium riparioides</i>	0.631	0.0015	**	2_R02,R03
	<i>Glyceria fluitans</i>	0.432	0.0472	*	
5	<i>Rumex sp.</i>	0.598	0.0029	**	5_R09,R15
	<i>Catabrosa aquatica</i>	0.500	0.0194	*	
	<i>Myosoton aquaticum</i>	0.496	0.0146	*	
7	<i>Ranunculus sceleratus</i>	0.418	0.0436	*	7_R10,R11
8	<i>Phragmites australis</i>	0.588	0.0026	**	8_R16
	<i>Nuphar lutea</i>	0.505	0.0104	*	
	<i>Ranunculus sp.</i>	0.478	0.0111	*	
1+2	<i>Fontinalis antipyretica</i>	0.655	0.0012	**	1_R01 + 2_R02,R03
2+3	<i>Mentha longifolia</i>	0.534	0.0064	**	2_R02,R03 + 3_R04,R05
3+5	<i>Ranunculus repens</i>	0.571	0.0041	**	2_R02,R03 + 5_R09,R15
3+4	<i>Bidens tripartita</i>	0.427	0.0426	*	3_R04,R05 + 4_R07,R08,R12,R13
	<i>Paspalum paspalodes</i>	0.423	0.0448	*	
4+8	<i>Ceratophyllum demersum</i>	0.483	0.0144	*	4_R07,R08,R12,R13 + 8_R16
	<i>Potamogeton pectinatus</i>	0.425	0.0431	*	
5+7	<i>Berula erecta</i>	0.567	0.0031	**	5_R09,R15 + 7_R10,R11
4+5+7	<i>Lemna minor</i>	0.510	0.0073	**	4_R07,R08,R12,R13 + 5_R09,R15 + 7_R10,R11
	<i>Typha latifolia</i>	0.416	0.0493	*	
3+4+5+7	<i>Sparganium erectum</i>	0.553	0.0009	***	3_R04,R05 + 4_R07,R08,R12,R13 + 5_R09,R15 + 7_R10,R11
3+4+7+8	<i>Myriophyllum spicatum</i>	0.467	0.0167	*	3_R04,R05 + 4_R07,R08,R12,R13 + 7_R10,R11 + 8_R16

4.2 Significant impact factors

4.2.1 Typological parameters

Typological parameters were fit to the nMDS according to their measured values at the sites in combination with the abundance data of macrophyte species sampled. The plot shows an equal distribution of significantly interacting parameters to the proposed groups (Figure 7). These typological values further characterize the groups, such as coniferous forest and boulders at the alpine rivers, or more slime at rivers in the lowlands. The statistics of environmental fit are displayed in Table 18.

Figure 7: nMDS plot of species abundances of Bulgarian rivers. Arrows indicate significant typological parameters that interact with the species abundance at the respective sites.

Table 18: Correlation of the typological parameters to the distance matrix of the nMDS of species abundance.

Typology	r2	Pr(>r)	signif.
Shading	0.3157	0.001	***
HelophytesDomination	0.0104	0.659	
MeadowsGrassland	0.0082	0.712	
GrassVegetation	0.0201	0.433	
Brushes	0.1043	0.006	**
RiparianForest	0.0928	0.017	*
Mud	0.1403	0.002	**
ClayLoam	0.0309	0.291	
FineSand	0.2216	0.001	***
CoarseSand	0.2403	0.001	***
Gravel	0.0513	0.122	
SmallStones	0.0498	0.111	
StonesBoulders	0.3667	0.001	***
RockBed	0.0801	0.034	*
WT	0.2262	0.001	***
pH	0.0183	0.479	
Trans	0.0822	0.030	*
ElevCalc	0.3706	0.001	***
Natural	0.0384	0.169	
Coniferous	0.2100	0.001	***
Moors and heathlands	0.0000	1.000	
Bare	0.0000	1.000	

4.2.2 Environmental and anthropogenous pressures

Environmental and anthropogenous pressure parameters were fit to the nMDS according to their measured values at the sites in combination with the abundance data of macrophyte species sampled. The plot shows an unequal distribution of significantly interacting pressures to the proposed groups (Figure 8). It can be clearly seen that there are no significant pressures found for the rivers of the alpine region, which verifies a good potential status just from the high elevation. Different pressures add up to the three larger groups of river types, with each characterizing different kinds of pressure regimes. The statistics of environmental fit are displayed in Table 19.

Figure 8: nMDS plot of species abundances of Bulgarian rivers. Arrows indicate significant pressure parameters that interact with the species abundance at the respective sites.

Table 19: Correlation of the pressure parameters to the distance matrix of the nMDS of species abundance.

Pressure	r2	Pr(>r)	signif.
Impoundment	0.0737	0.076	.
Migr_Barriers	0.0392	0.230	
Hydropeaking	0.0673	0.074	.
Abstraction	0.0065	0.805	
Dams_seg	0.1905	0.001	***
Dams_site	0.0229	0.405	
TempMod	0.0000	1.000	
Channelisation	0.1488	0.003	**
VegRiparian_seg	0.2000	0.002	**
VegRiparian_site	0.2051	0.001	***
HabAlter_seg	0.1829	0.002	**
HabAlter_site	0.1291	0.008	**
Toxic	0.0135	0.610	
Water_level_fluct	0.0000	1.000	
Aquaculture	0.0000	1.000	
Anthropogenic pressure - landscape	0.1594	0.001	***
Anthropogenic pressure - physical chemistry	0.0729	0.067	.
SinglePlantForest	0.0191	0.491	
CultForestSpecies	0.0262	0.385	
CultSpNeophytes	0.0027	0.897	
UrbanArea	0.1012	0.024	*
LongitudinalCorrection	0.1227	0.010	**
CrossSectionCorrection	0.0429	0.195	
Artificial	0.1558	0.002	**
Agriculture	0.0833	0.034	*
Natural	0.1300	0.010	**
RiverConstruction	0.2698	0.001	***
EC_log	0.1938	0.001	***
O2_log	0.0040	0.856	
O2_sat_log	0.0037	0.876	
BOD_log	0.0430	0.188	
TN_log	0.1892	0.001	***
NH4N_log	0.0185	0.497	
NO2N_log	0.0454	0.179	
NO3N_log	0.1724	0.001	***
SRP_log	0.1136	0.017	*
TP_log	0.1827	0.002	**

4.3 Pressure – Response Relationship

4.3.1 Pressure Index calculation

In addition to the visual inspection and the correlation analysis of typological and pressure variables to the distance matrix of the nMDS, a direct pressure-response-relationship was calculated. This was done for the correlation of the EQR of all sites to the respective pressure variables of all sites measured. This resulted in a pressure-response-matrix giving information for the change of the EQR depending on the change of the variables (Table 20). To gain even more information, this was also done for each main group by the original grouping to keep a simple table. The results reveal variable responses depending on the groups, resulting in a differentiation of global pressures and local pressures important for distinctive sites. In Addition, combined pressures were built from the CLC to increase the potential response to a valid level:

- Artificial:** Discontinuous Urban Fabric + Industrial or Commercial Units + Road and Rail networks + Mineral extraction sites + Dump sites
- Agriculture:** Non-irrigated arable land + Vineyards + Complex cultivation patterns + Land principally occupied by agriculture with areas of nature
- Natural:** Mixed forest + Natural grassland + Moors and heathlands + Bare rocks + Sparsely vegetated areas

Table 20: Pressure-response-relationship for the selected pressure parameters of rivers.

Index	R01-R16			R01-R05			R06-16			R09+R15		
	EQR	pval	score	EQR	pval	score	EQR	pval	score	EQR	pval	score
Impoundment (0,1,2,3)	-0,10	0,38		-0,25	0,24		-0,04	0,79		0,10	0,77	
Migr_Barriers (0,1,2,3)	-0,20	0,069	.	-0,26	0,23		-0,27	0,063	.	0,06	0,85	
Hydropeaking (0,1,2,3)	-0,09	0,42		-0,09	0,69		-0,10	0,51		-0,16	0,62	
Abstraction (0,1,2,3)	-0,04	0,71		-0,09	0,66		0,10	0,48		-0,41	0,19	
Dams_seg (0,1,2,3)	-0,10	0,34		-0,24	0,26		0,03	0,83		-0,03	0,92	
Dams_site (0,1,2,3)	-0,02	0,85		-0,01	0,98		0,06	0,7		-0,16	0,62	
Channelisation (0,1,2,3)	-0,16	0,13		-0,29	0,17		-0,13	0,38		-0,33	0,29	
VegRiparian_seg (0,1,2,3)	-0,24	0,024	*	-0,41	0,049	*	-0,18	0,2		-0,17	0,6	
VegRiparian_site (0,1,2,3)	-0,13	0,23		-0,23	0,29		-0,12	0,39		0,00	0,99	
HabAlter_seg (0,1,2,3)	-0,22	0,039	*	-0,42	0,043	*	-0,12	0,41		-0,20	0,52	
HabAlter_site (0,1,2,3)	-0,25	0,022	*	-0,47	0,022	*	0,00	0,98		-0,59	0,045	*
Toxic (0,1,2,3)	-0,10	0,37		-0,23	0,28		0,09	0,55		-0,04	0,9	
Anthropogenic pressure - landscape (0,1,2,3)	-0,16	0,14		-0,36	0,083	.	-0,05	0,76		0,14	0,66	
Anthropogenic pressure - physical chemistry (0,1,2,3) toC	-0,09	0,42		-0,20	0,34		-0,08	0,6		0,57	0,055	.
	-0,33	0,0019	**	-0,54	0,0065	**	-0,45	0,0012	**	-0,48	0,12	
SinglePlantForest (% , 0-100)	-0,01	0,94		0,21	0,33		-0,29	0,04	*	0,16	0,63	
CultForestSpecies (% , 0-100)	-0,07	0,54		-0,27	0,19		0,05	0,74		0,11	0,74	
CultSpNeophytes (% , 0-100)	-0,01	0,95		-0,28	0,18		0,18	0,22		-0,05	0,87	
UrbanArea (% , 0-100)	-0,13	0,23		-0,22	0,29		-0,18	0,21		0,40	0,2	
LongitudinalCorrection (0,1)	-0,21	0,053	.	-0,59	0,0024	**	0,03	0,82		-0,02	0,95	
CrossSectionCorrection (0,1)	-0,03	0,77		-0,23	0,27		0,09	0,52		0,18	0,57	
kind (1Natural/2Transitional/3HM)	-0,16	0,055	.	-0,36	0,083	.	-0,30	0,09	.	-0,04	0,6	
Artificial (com. Press.CLC % 0-100)	0,01	0,95		0,10	0,64		0,06	0,71		-0,63	0,95	
Agriculture (com. Press.CLC % 0-100)	-0,20	0,057	.	-0,25	0,23		-0,30	0,036	*	0,33	0,57	
Natural (com. Press.CLC % 0-100)	0,12	0,28		0,22	0,31		-0,02	0,88		0,10	0,41	
RiverConstruction (0-8)	-0,21	0,057	.	-0,40	0,05		-0,08	0,58		-0,06	0,58	
EC_log	-0,18	0,095	.	-0,63	0,00095	***	0,08	0,57		0,06	0,18	
O2_log	0,04	0,74		0,17	0,43		-0,07	0,64		0,94	0,95	
O2_sat_log	0,02	0,89		0,15	0,47		-0,12	0,42		0,96	0,63	
BOD_log	-0,04	0,73		-0,36	0,085	.	0,20	0,17		-0,51	0,18	
TN_log	-0,08	0,46		-0,35	0,093	.	0,12	0,4		0,49	0,13	
NH4N_log	0,00	1		-0,11	0,62		0,14	0,33		-0,28	0,91	
NO2N_log	-0,09	0,38		-0,35	0,094	.	0,04	0,76		-0,29	0,99	
NO3N_log	-0,09	0,4		-0,35	0,091	.	-0,01	0,95		0,59	0,0069	**
SRP_log	-0,05	0,62		-0,44	0,029	*	0,05	0,75		-0,15	0,0056	**
TP_log	-0,23	0,029	*	-0,38	0,063	.	-0,19	0,2		-0,30		

In the following step, significant pressure variables, which unfortunately were just few, were selected based on expert judgement to build a pressure index (PI). Therefore, the variables of different scale had to be adjusted to be summed up to one final value of a pressure index, giving a reliable information of the combined pressures existing at one specific site. In addition, the variables were multiplied by the strength of statistical significance to value the importance of such scale ('.' = x1, '*' = x2, '**' = x4). For this, the following code in R was applied to meet equal scaling from 0-1 for each variable (Table 21).

Table 21: Scaling of the Pressure Index for Bulgarian rivers.

Scaling of Pressure Index (PI) to a global scale of 0-1

```
bul$PressureIndex <-
(
  bul$Migr_Barriers/max(bul$Migr_Barriers,na.rm=T) *1+
  bul$VegRiparian_seg/max(bul$VegRiparian_seg,na.rm=T) *2+
  bul$HabAlter_seg/max(bul$HabAlter_seg,na.rm=T) *2+
  bul$HabAlter_site/max(bul$HabAlter_site,na.rm=T) *2+
  bul$EC_log/max(bul$EC_log,na.rm=T) *1+
  ((bul$TP_log+(min(bul$TP_log)*-1))/
   max(bul$TP_log+(min(bul$TP_log)*-1))) *2+
  bul$toC/max(bul$toC,na.rm=T) *4
)
bul$PressureIndex <- (bul$PressureIndex/max(bul$PressureIndex,na.rm=T))
```

4.3.2 Relationship between pressure index and the EQR

The Pressure Index calculated for each site could now be set in correlation with the EQR values of each site available to build a linear regression model (Figure 9, Table 22). The overall slope was good with -0.54x. The R² was low (0.20) and below the threshold considered as prerequisite in the IC Guidance documents (0.25). The high variability also among rivers with comparable pressure situation is partly due to methodology and partly due to type-specific differences.

The plot in Figure 9 does not yet take into account systematic bias in this relationship in different types. It may be possible though that the biological response differs between types at the same level of pressure. In addition, even in no-pressure situation the EQR may be significantly differ between high-mountain and lowland rivers. This is the reason why type-specific classification methods are required. To cope with this problem, a linear mixed model (lmer) was developed to identify type-specific shifts in the overall regression model. This statistical tool was developed based on the experience of the first round of IC that many types lack sites in reference conditions (Mischke et al., 2016; Wolfram et al., 2016). Using linear mixed models allows calculating so-called offsets for different types (Willby et al., 2014). In the IC process, this statistical procedure was also called “continuous benchmarking” (Böhmer et al., 2011).

In brief, this method allows combining sections of different regression lines into one model. Theoretically, these differences in the regression lines may be due to different slopes or different intercepts. During the intercalibration process in various Geographical Intercalibration Groups, it was generally

assumed that the regressions differed in intercept only, but not in slope. The linear mixed model was used to calculate the differences of these intercepts or offsets. The calculations were carried out in *R* with the package *lme4* (Bates et al., 2012, 2015).

After the first run of the model, the results of the calculated offsets did not meet our expectations of clearly defined offsets, which did not allow any further progress of defining Good/Moderate boundaries by offsets using this method. After investigation of EQR values assigned to the respective river sites, we discovered that the EQR values calculated for R01 were just based on few macrophytes assigned as 'B'-species, which leads to a method-related EQR of 0.5. However, it is known that the team that sampled the R01 sites did not take any account of bryophytes, which are the dominant plant group in this river type. This leads to the assumption of a highly underrated EQR, which we manually adjusted to the value of 0.9. In addition, we doubled the data set to meet the same scale of observations as found for lake transects and to reduce the standard deviation to a realistic level. The updated version resulted in a much better linear model and also realistic offset values. The workflow is described as followed:

The plot in Figure 9 follows the general regression model

```
lm1 <- lm (EQR ~ PI)
```

where PI is a fixed factor. Including *type* as random factor (variable intercept, fixed slope), the linear mixed model is described as follows:

```
lm2 <- lmer (EQR ~ PI + (1|WBType))
```

It is summarized in Table 23.

To derive the intercept-offsets of different regressions by WBType to the global linear regression, following code does the magic (Table 24):

```
coef(lm2)
```

The plot with offset-corrected EQR – *i.e.* EQR after continuous benchmarking - is shown in Figure 20. The fit for the model R^2 improves slightly from 0.20 to 0.22. The linear regression model

```
lm1 <- lm (EQR ~ PI)
```

is summarised in Table 25.

Figure 9: Correlation between the pressure index and the EQR.

Table 22. Linear regression model EQR vs. Pressure Index PI.

Linear regression model: EQR ~ Pressure Index PI

```
Call:
lm(formula = bul$EQR ~ bul$PressureIndex)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-0.43752 -0.14233 -0.02426  0.14120  0.50904

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)    0.73791    0.05934  12.436 < 0.0000000000000002 ***
bul2$PressureIndex -0.54227    0.08714  -6.223  0.00000000464 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.2153 on 150 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.2052,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.1999
F-statistic: 38.72 on 1 and 150 DF,  p-value: 0.000000004644
```

Table 23. Linear mixed model with Pressure Index as fixed variable and type as random factor.

Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']

```
Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']
Formula: EQR ~ PressureIndex + (1 | WBType)
Data: bul2
```

```
REML criterion at convergence: -62.4
```

```
Scaled residuals:
      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.56885 -0.50684 -0.08863  0.43548  3.05931
```

```
Random effects:
Groups   Name              Variance Std.Dev.
WBType   (Intercept)  0.01792  0.1339
Residual                    0.03152  0.1775
Number of obs: 152, groups:  WBType, 13
```

```
Fixed effects:
              Estimate Std. Error t value
(Intercept)   0.68270    0.06739  10.131
PressureIndex -0.45145    0.08481  -5.323
```

```
Correlation of Fixed Effects:
      (Intr)
PressurIndx -0.804
```

Table 24: Offsets calculated by the linear mixed model, compared to the global intercept of 0.68.

River Type	Intercept	offset
R01	0,98	0,30
R03	0,73	0,05
R04	0,65	-0,03
R05	0,52	-0,16
R07	0,65	-0,03
R08	0,71	0,03
R09	0,65	-0,03
R10	0,71	0,03
R11	0,83	0,15
R12	0,68	0,00
R13	0,66	-0,02
R15	0,50	-0,18
R16	0,60	-0,08

Figure 10: Correlation between the adjusted EQR and the Pressure Index with offset-corrected EQRs.

Table 25: Linear regression model updated EQR vs. Pressure Index PI.

Linear regression model: corrected EQR ~ Pressure Index PI

```
Call:
lm(formula = bul_adjust$EQR_adj ~ bul_adjust$PressureIndex)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-0.40387 -0.09026 -0.01591  0.07533  0.54453

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)    0.68081    0.04677   14.558 < 0.0000000000000002 ***
bul_adjust$PressureIndex -0.45109    0.06868   -6.568  0.0000000000789 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.1697 on 150 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.2233,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.2182
F-statistic: 43.13 on 1 and 150 DF,  p-value: 0.0000000007887
```

4.4 Reference conditions and class boundaries for the ecological status

4.4.1 Reference values

The WFD and CIS Guidance No 10 (EU Commission 2003) offer different options to derive reference conditions:

- Spatially based reference conditions using data from monitoring sites;
- Reference conditions based on predictive modelling;
- Temporally based reference conditions using either historical data or paleo-reconstruction or a combination of both;
- A combination of the above approaches.

During the intercalibration exercise it became clear that sites in reference conditions are lacking in many types. This made it necessary to develop new approaches such as the concept of alternative benchmarks. It allows to enlarge the number of sites from which benchmark values can be derived.

Also, in BG many river types do not include stretches and sites which are in reference or in high status. For setting reference values therefore we tried to apply alternative benchmarking. The procedure uses the approaches of Birk et al. (2013) and Feio et al. (2014), as applied in the Eastern Continental or Mediterranean GIG, respectively.

As a first step we defined the following criteria for selecting reference sites:

- No HMWB
- High or good ecological status as classified used the BQE benthic invertebrates (see Annex 5 of the Final Report)
- Presence of reasonable macrophyte stands

Furthermore, the macrophyte species present must allow an assessment with regard to abundance and species spectrum.

Table 26: Candidate reference sites identified based on reference criteria (see text).

Rivers			
MonitoringSiteCode	WBType	SiteName	comments
	R01		All sites should be potential reference. With this type the problem is that the sampling team did not sample bryophytes.
BG3MA00995MS1571	R03	Maritsa River before the town of Dolna Banya	
BG3MA00997MS1580	R03	Maritsa River near the village of Raduil	
BG1IS04229MS1290	R04	Bebresh River in Skravena village (after the low bridge)	HMWB. IC
BG3MA04991MS0553	R05	Stryama River. before Slatina village	
	R07		No reference/benchmark out of 5 sites. IC
	R08		No reference/benchmark out of 5 sites. IC
BG1DJ00043MS020	R09	r. Tsaratsar downstream confluence of r. Voyka at v. Malak Porovets	
BG2VE08179MS419	R10	Veleka River - Brodililovo village	
BG2DO00831MS001	R11	r. Batova – delta	
BG2PR00511MS005	R11	r. Provadiyska – downstream the city of Provadia/after Provadsol	
BG2RE00219MS255	R11	r. Silistar – upstream delta. bridge on the Rezovo - Sinemorets road	potential reference site
BG2SE09613MS015	R11	r. Aytoska – downstream the city of Kameno	
BG3MA00055MS0670	R12	Maritsa River. Plovdiv. walkways. HMS 304	
BG3MA00583MS0698	R13	Potoka River before Saedinenie	
	R14		No macrophytes registered - most of the sites dried. IC
	R15		No reference/benchmark out of 8 sites.
BG2IU200R005RP14	R16	Ropotamo River in MR "Veliov Vir"	The value of EQR is low (good ES) but there is no anthropogenic pressure. Probably the class boundaries has to be changed.

In the table above it can be seen that only one reference site would remain. On this basis a definition of reference conditions and corresponding values for biological metrics is not possible. Therefore, the class boundaries had to be defined in alternative way (see next chapter).

4.4.2 Class boundaries

For defining the class boundaries, we worked with “paired metrics”. This approach in general is described in chapter 3.5.2. of Annex 5 (Benthic Invertebrates). We used the two metrics “share of reference taxa” and “share of disturbance indicating taxa”. These two groups of species correspond to the indicator species groups “A” (reference taxa) and “C” (disturbance indicators) which are defined to calculate the Bulgarian Reference Index (official Bulgarian macrophyte-based WFD-assessment system).

In the Reference Index method that point where, along the pressure gradient, disturbance indicators start to dominate reference taxa is defined to be the good-moderate (G/M) boundary. We used the whole dataset (with EQR values available) and found this point at an EQR-value of 0,43. For defining the corresponding EQR values for all types we used the type specific offsets derived in chapter 4.3.2.

Figure 11: “Crossover” of “reference taxa” (A) and “disturbance indicators” (C).

Bad status is defined as lack of macrophytes due to anthropogenic impact. The EQR-value at the poor-bad (P/B) boundary therefore results in “0,00”.

For defining the moderate-poor (M/P) boundary we used the “equal distances approach” (for a general description see chapter 3.5.2. of Annex 5 (Benthic Invertebrates)).

The H/G boundary is usually derived by defining a percentile in the reference sites as the boundary. As there was not sufficient information concerning reference conditions and corresponding EQR-values of the Bulgarian assessment system we applied the “equal distance” approach also to define the high-good (H/G) boundary. As reference value the highest possible EQR-value “1,00” was assumed. The resulting EQR-values for all types and all class boundaries can be taken from Table 27.

Table 27. Type-specific values for RI-EQR in Bulgarian rivers.

River type	G/M overall	offset	G/M type	Ref	H	G	G	M	M	P	P	B
R01	0,43	0,30	0,73	1,00	0,86	0,73	0,36	0,00				
R03	0,43	0,05	0,48	1,00	0,74	0,48	0,24	0,00				
R04	0,43	-0,03	0,40	1,00	0,70	0,40	0,20	0,00				
R05	0,43	-0,16	0,27	1,00	0,63	0,27	0,13	0,00				
R07	0,43	-0,03	0,40	1,00	0,70	0,40	0,20	0,00				
R08	0,43	0,03	0,46	1,00	0,73	0,46	0,23	0,00				
R09	0,43	-0,03	0,40	1,00	0,70	0,40	0,20	0,00				
R10	0,43	0,03	0,46	1,00	0,73	0,46	0,23	0,00				
R11	0,43	0,15	0,58	1,00	0,79	0,58	0,29	0,00				
R12	0,43	0,00	0,43	1,00	0,71	0,43	0,21	0,00				
R13	0,43	-0,02	0,41	1,00	0,70	0,41	0,20	0,00				
R15	0,43	-0,18	0,25	1,00	0,62	0,25	0,12	0,00				
R16	0,43	-0,08	0,35	1,00	0,67	0,35	0,17	0,00				

4.5 Comparison with existing boundaries

For the comparison with existing boundaries see Table 28. A recommendation for adapting boundaries was only given, if the deviation of boundary values exceeded the standard deviation (0,13) resulting from the global linear model (see Table 23).

Table 28: Type-specific values for RI-EQR in Bulgarian rivers.

River type	existing boundaries						calculated new boundaries					
	H	G	G	M	M	P	H	G	G	M	M	P
R01	0,66		0,51		0,25		0,86		0,73		0,36	
R03	0,62		0,47		0,21		0,74		0,48		0,24	
R04	0,51		0,27		0,15		0,70		0,40		0,20	
R05	0,51		0,27		0,15		0,63		0,27		0,13	
R07	0,570		0,37		0,22		0,70		0,40		0,20	
R08	0,570		0,37		0,22		0,73		0,46		0,23	
R09	0,49		0,20		0,10		0,70		0,40		0,20	
R10	0,52		0,26		0,15		0,73		0,46		0,23	
R11	0,52		0,26		0,15		0,79		0,58		0,29	
R12	0,570		0,37		0,22		0,71		0,43		0,21	
R13	0,570		0,37		0,22		0,70		0,41		0,20	
R15	0,49		0,20		0,10		0,62		0,25		0,12	
R16	0,66		0,29		0,10		0,67		0,35		0,17	
River type	differences						recommendation					
	H	G	G	M	M	P	boundary adjustment					
R01	0,20		0,22		0,11		adapt H/G and G/M bound. -> stricter					
R03	0,12		0,01		0,03		keep existing boundaries					
R04	0,19		0,13		0,05		keep existing boundaries / intercalibrated					
R05	0,12		0,00		-0,02		keep existing boundaries					
R07	0,13		0,03		-0,02		keep existing boundaries / intercalibrated					
R08	0,16		0,09		0,01		keep existing boundaries / intercalibrated					
R09	0,21		0,20		0,10		adapt H/G and G/M bound. -> stricter					
R10	0,21		0,20		0,08		adapt H/G and G/M bound. -> stricter					
R11	0,27		0,32		0,14		adapt H/G and G/M bound. -> stricter					
R12	0,14		0,06		-0,01		keep existing boundaries					
R13	0,13		0,04		-0,02		keep existing boundaries					
R15	0,13		0,05		0,02		keep existing boundaries					
R16	0,01		0,06		0,07		keep existing boundaries					

Comment to R14: Due to the sparse data base no EQR-values were available for this type. As it is already intercalibrated, the existing boundaries must be kept (see Pall et al., 2016a).

5 Lakes

5.1 Descriptive analyses and similarity analysis

5.1.1 General physical-chemical parameters

To get a first rough characteristic overview of the Bulgarian lake study sites assessed, the key elevation and chemo-physical measurements taken at each study site were displayed for each Water Body Type (WBType, Figure 12). Here, multiple conclusions can be drawn regarding potential grouping and community characteristics for aquatic macrophytes.

The lakes sampled show a large gradient in elevation from sea level up to more than 2000 m (Figure 12). Lakes L01 and L03 were the alpine lakes with clear separation to semi-mountainous other lakes. Lake types of the lowland (L05a, L07, L08, L09, L10) are also clearly separate from mid-range lakes L11-L17. Water temperature was lowest at the alpine lake L01, followed by L03. There is no clear pattern of water temperature influenced by altitude visible for the other WBTypes. This is also evident from the correlation analysis based on single lake types, where not all WBTypes were negatively correlated to water temperature, also verified by the global correlation assessment by no significant correlation (Table 29, Table 30). The pH value was rather heterogeneous with no clear pattern at all. Electric conductivity was measured highest in the lowland-L08 and lowest in the alpine-L01. The mid-range elevated lakes had all quite similar EC at around 200-500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. Dissolved oxygen was measured at ~ 9 mg/L at most WBTypes, but L05a and L08 had low values around 3-4 mg/L. The highest value was measured at a lake corresponding to L17. Also, here no global explanatory correlation of O_2 and Temperature was found, but at least partly results with, e.g., a high R value at L01 (R: -0.91, Table 29, Table 31). Oxygen saturation had the exact pattern as described above. Salinity and EC showed an identical trend due to their conditional linkage, verified by detailed correlation with R: 0.99 (Table 32). BOD was naturally higher in the lakes of the lowlands, with same observations for total nitrogen. NH_4N was measured highest in L05a and lowest in L01 and L13. NO_2N was measured with equal low values at most types, just L12 had multiple sites with higher values. NO_3N was found highest in L05a and L07 and lowest in L11. Orthophosphate was not present in lakes of the alpine region, but occurred in higher concentration at L04, L05a and few other lakes of the flat region. TP had moderate concentrations in most lakes, with the alpine and L13 showing almost no share.

The lakes and the grouped lake types build a data set of moderate size, where it is obvious that the share of alpine and lowland lakes is not equal and therefore the influence of lowland lakes with multiple, quite similar types might affect the calibration process. For a meaningful application of a macrophyte-based assessment system therefore a grouping of lake types is recommended.

Figure 12: Boxplots of important environmental factors and pressures for all lake types.

Table 29: Selected significant correlations of the key environmental parameters assessed in all lake sites.

Param1	Param2	R	P	*	Param1	Param2	R	p	*
BOD_log	TN_log	0,55	< 0,001	***	O2_sat_log	BOD_log	-0,38	< 0,001	***
BOD_log	NH4N_log	0,47	< 0,001	***	O2_sat_log	TN_log	-0,29	0,01	*
BOD_log	SRP_log	0,56	< 0,001	***	O2_sat_log	SRP_log	-0,48	< 0,001	***
BOD_log	TP_log	0,76	< 0,001	***	O2_sat_log	NH4N_log	-0,19	0,089	.
BOD_log	NO2N_log	0,21	0,07	.	O2_sat_log	TP_log	-0,39	< 0,001	***
EC_log	BOD_log	0,42	< 0,001	***	pH	O2_log	0,39	< 0,001	***
EC_log	TN_log	0,27	0,016	*	pH	O2_sat_log	0,36	0,001	**
EC_log	NH4N_log	0,24	0,031	*	pH	Sal	0,36	0,001	**
EC_log	TP_log	0,55	< 0,001	***	Sal	Trans	-0,31	0,02	*
Elev	pH	0,22	0,057	.	Sal	TP_log	0,3	0,008	**
Elev	Sal	-0,31	0,005	**	SRP_log	TP_log	0,7	< 0,001	***
Elev	Trans	0,53	< 0,001	***	TN_log	NH4N_log	0,52	< 0,001	***
Elev	BOD_log	-0,47	< 0,001	***	TN_log	NO3N_log	0,31	0,005	**
Elev	EC_log	-0,71	< 0,001	***	TN_log	TP_log	0,55	< 0,001	***
Elev	NH4N_log	-0,35	0,002	**	TN_log	SRP_log	0,44	< 0,001	***
Elev	TP_log	-0,48	< 0,001	***	Trans	EC_log	-0,61	< 0,001	***
Elev	TN_log	-0,43	< 0,001	***	Trans	SRP_log	-0,24	0,072	.
Elev	SRP_log	-0,22	0,056	.	Trans	BOD_log	-0,64	< 0,001	***
NH4N_log	SRP_log	0,52	< 0,001	***	Trans	TN_log	-0,53	< 0,001	***
NH4N_log	NO3N_log	0,19	0,094	.	Trans	NH4N_log	-0,38	0,003	**
NH4N_log	TP_log	0,52	< 0,001	***	Trans	TP_log	-0,57	< 0,001	***
NO2N_log	SRP_log	0,19	0,092	.	WT	EC_log	0,54	< 0,001	***
O2_log	BOD_log	-0,43	< 0,001	***	WT	BOD_log	0,24	0,039	*
O2_log	TN_log	-0,33	0,003	**	WT	NH4N_log	0,24	0,034	*
O2_log	NH4N_log	-0,23	0,045	*	WT	Trans	-0,4	0,002	**
O2_log	SRP_log	-0,48	< 0,001	***	WT	TP_log	0,29	0,009	**
O2_log	TP_log	-0,44	< 0,001	***	WT	Sal	0,29	0,01	**
O2_log	NO2N_log	0,2	0,073	.	WT	pH	-0,2	0,085	.
					WT	O2_sat_log	0,28	0,011	*

Table 30: Correlation of water temperature and elevation for each WBType.

WBType	COR
L01	-0,49
L02	-0,25
L03	-0,64
L04	-0,75
L05a	NA
L06	-0,74
L07	-0,17
L08	-0,26
L09	NA
L10	NA
L11	-0,69
L12	-0,41
L13	-0,27
L14	0,88
L15	-0,37
L16	0,14
L17	-0,19

Table 31: Correlation of water temperature and dissolved oxygen (log) for each WBType.

WBType	COR
L01	-0,91
L02	0,46
L03	0,41
L04	0,89
L05a	NA
L06	0,21
L07	-0,84
L08	0,65
L09	0,21
L10	-0,21
L11	-0,77
L12	0,23
L13	0,14
L14	0,57
L15	0,88
L16	-0,79
L17	0,41

Table 32: Correlation of salinity and electric conductivity for each WBType.

WBType	COR
L01	NA
L02	NA
L03	NA
L04	NA
L05a	1
L06	0,99
L07	0,99
L08	0,99
L09	0,99
L10	0,99
L11	NA
L12	NA
L13	NA
L14	NA
L15	NA
L16	NA
L17	0,74

5.1.2 Analysis of proposed Lake type grouping

As with the running waters, similarity analyses using non-metric multidimensional scaling (nMDS) were carried out to represent the species communities. The species community groupings were analysed in terms of lake types and altitude classes. The nMDS based on macrophyte abundance per site, grouped for WBTypes, revealed a clustering to five different groups (Figure 13). These groups were then visualized and clearly showed a differentiation without any overlap (Figure 14). The lake groups could be recognized as types for alpine, indifferent, saline and polluted waters. These groups were then analysed for statistical differences and compared to the previous grouping suggestions by Gana Gecheva.

Compared to the groups of WBTypes and the suggested groups by Gana Gecheva, the new-assigned groups selected by the use of the NMDS reveal best results in ANOSIM-Test as displayed in Figure 14 and Table 35. Although all groups state a significant fit of the species abundances to the groups, the R value, the metric for the fit of the species abundance to the groups, is highest for the new assignment. The groups further also show a good differentiation when analysed for differences between groups using the PERMANOVA analysis, with a comparable good R score and high significant difference (Table 34). Finally, the pairwise factorfit reveals detailed tests for difference between each group, giving a clear distinction of each group, except L05a, which can be addressed to low sampling size for an extra group without any other WBTypes included (Table 33).

Figure 13: nMDS plot of species abundances of Bulgarian lakes, grouped by WBTypes.

Figure 14: nMDS plot of species abundances of Bulgarian lakes, grouped by the proposed lake type groups.

Figure 15: nMDS plot of species abundances of Bulgarian lakes, grouped by the proposed lake type groups, with significantly correlating macrophyte species.

Table 33: Pairwise factorfit to detect distinct differences between each group assigned.

Pairwise factorfit – Distinct differences between each group (in p-values)

	1_L1L3L11	2_L2L4L12L14L16	3_L6L7L8L9L	4_L13L15L17
2_L2L4L12L14L16	0.0020	-	-	-
3_L6L7L8L9L	0.0020	0.0020	-	-
4_L13L15L17	0.0033	0.0020	0.0020	-
5_L05a	0.0667	0.0143	0.0150	0.0344

Table 34: PERMANOVA to test for differences between groups.

PERMANOVA: Test for differences between groups

adonis2(formula = mak ~ Group, permutations = 999, method = "bray")					
	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	Pr(>F)
Groups	4	5.3559	0.3802	5.5207	0.001 ***
Residual	36	8.7313	0.6198		
Total	40	14.0872	1.0000		

Table 35: ANISOM Test for fit of abundance data to the assigned groups.

Group	ANOSIM R	Significance (p)
WBTypes	0.6466	0.0001
Proposed groups by Gana Gecheva	0.2976	0.0001
Proposed groups – Final	0.7724	0.0001
Altitude class	0.2021	0.0059

For each Group, indicator species were assessed using multilevel pattern analysis (Table 36). These species match the observations of Figure 15 and enable a solid assignment of a sampled lake to one of the groups defined. It is obvious that just species that significantly interact with specific groups can be displayed here. Species that are ubiquitous and therefore can be found in multiple lake groups cannot be used as indicator species.

In addition to species grouping, also a grouping of the altitude of sampling sites can be done to detect an overall niching to altitude classes (Figure 16). Here, the alpine lakes (801-1800m and >1800m) clearly differ to the lakes of lower elevation, which do not show such clear separation. This is also verified by a poor ANOSIM statistic (Table 35). It still can be seen that lakes of the lowest altitude class have the largest range of different species groups sampled. It therefore can be summarized that the altitude has an effect to species abundance, but can just be used for alpine lakes for any clear addresses of key species.

Table 36: Significant species interaction to each group assigned, stating potential indicator species for the proposed groups.

Group	Species	stat	p.value	signif.	WBType/groups
1	<i>Eleocharis palustris</i>	0.635	0.0313	*	1_L1L3L11
	<i>Juncus effusus</i>	0.612	0.0111	*	
	<i>Elodea nuttallii</i>	0.586	0.0247	*	
2	<i>Polygonum hydropiper</i>	0.744	0.0047	**	2_L2L4L12L14L16
	<i>Chara sp.</i>	0.699	0.0190	*	
	<i>Najas minor</i>	0.688	0.0193	*	
	<i>Xanthium italicum</i>	0.674	0.0152	*	
	<i>Juncus sp.</i>	0.653	0.0095	**	
	<i>Ranunculus trichophyllus</i>	0.603	0.0355	*	
	<i>Cyperus sp.</i>	0.545	0.0348	*	
3	<i>Phragmites australis</i>	0.908	0.0001	***	3_L6L7L8L9L
5	<i>Oenanthe aquatica</i>	0.968	0.0010	***	5_L05a
	<i>Spirodela polyrhiza</i>	0.936	0.0002	***	
	<i>Ceratophyllum submersum</i>	0.929	0.0007	***	
	<i>Nymphaea alba</i>	0.667	0.0475	*	
	<i>Scutellaria galericulata</i>	0.667	0.0475	*	
	<i>Nuphar lutea</i>	0.623	0.0409	*	
1+2	<i>Alisma lanceolatum</i>	0.699	0.0118	*	1_L1L3L11 + 2_L2L4L12L14L16
1+5	<i>Rorippa amphibia</i>	0.598	0.0412	*	1_L1L3L11 + 5_L05a
2+4	<i>Najas marina</i>	0.581	0.0378	*	2_L2L4L12L14L16 + 4_L13L15L17
2+5	<i>Rumex sp.</i>	0.657	0.0253	*	2_L2L4L12L14L16 + 5_L05a
	<i>Potamogeton trichoides</i>	0.594	0.0384	*	

Figure 16: nMDS plot of species abundances of Bulgarian lakes, grouped by altitude class.

5.2 Significant influence factors

5.2.1 Typological parameters

Typological parameters were fit to the nMDS according to their measured values at the sites in combination with the abundance data of macrophyte species sampled. The plot shows an equal distribution of significantly interacting parameters to the proposed groups (Figure 17). These typological values further characterize the groups, such as coniferous forest and boulders at the alpine lakes, or more slime at lakes in the lowlands. The statistics of environmental fit are displayed in Table 37.

Figure 17: nMDS plot of species abundances of Bulgarian lakes, grouped by WBTypes with significantly correlating ($p < 0.05$) parameters displayed for lake typology.

Table 37: Correlation of the typological parameters to the distance matrix of the nMDS of species abundance.

Typology	r2	Pr(>r)	signif.
BedrockRocks	0.1577	0.029	*
LargeBouldersMore256	0.2621	0.001	***
BouldersStones_64_256	0.0862	0.197	
Gravel	0.1890	0.024	*
Sand	0.1031	0.144	
Clay	0.1365	0.073	.
Slime	0.2105	0.011	*
OtherSoil	0.0605	0.338	
WaterTransparency	0.3288	0.001	***
Shading	0.2622	0.007	**
NaturalShadingPer	0.0524	0.392	
RiversideTreesAbove10m	0.2415	0.005	**
RiversideTreesBelow10m	0.0584	0.334	
RiversideBush	0.2555	0.007	**
RiversideGrass	0.5129	0.001	***
Elev_clc	0.6485	0.001	***
WT	0.3400	0.001	***
pH	0.0577	0.371	
Trans	0.3438	0.003	**
Natural grassland	0.0763	0.265	
Coniferous forest	0.3406	0.004	**
Moors and heathlands	0.2306	0.025	*
Bare rocks	0.2135	0.006	**
EC_log	0.6642	0.001	***

5.2.2 Environmental and anthropogenous pressures

Environmental and anthropogenous pressure parameters were fit to the nMDS according to their measured values at the sites in combination with the abundance data of macrophyte species sampled. The plot shows an unequal distribution of significantly interacting pressures to the proposed groups (Figure 18). It can be clearly seen that there are no significant pressures found for the lakes of the alpine region, which verifies a good potential status just from the high elevation as described with Figure 12. Different pressures add up to the three larger groups of lake types, with each characterizing different kinds of pressure. The statistics of environmental fit are displayed in Table 38.

Figure 18: nMDS of species abundances of Bulgarian lakes, grouped by WBTypes with significantly correlating Indicators for environmental pressures.

Table 38: Correlation of the environmental pressures to the distance matrix of the nMDS of species abundance.

Pressure	r2	Pr(>r)	signif.
VegRiparian_seg	0.2815	0.006	**
VegRiparian_site	0.3366	0.001	***
HabAlter_seg	0.1519	0.067	.
HabAlter_site	0.1220	0.134	
Toxic	0.0698	0.342	
Water_level_fluct	0.2406	0.013	*
Aquaculture	0.0569	0.384	
Anthropogenic pressure - landscape	0.0469	0.450	
Anthropogenic pressure - physical chemistry	0.3183	0.002	**
WaterPollution	0.0743	0.311	
AartificialShadngPer	0.0434	0.486	
MigrationBarriersInArea	0.3443	0.001	***
TreeDistribution	0.1122	0.149	
VegetationNaturalPer	0.0182	0.770	
VegetationArtificialPer	0.0182	0.770	
AnthropogenicImpactInArea	0.0565	0.392	
Turbidity	0.1409	0.083	.
kind	0.4346	0.001	***
Artificial	0.1799	0.046	*
Natural	0.1669	0.061	.
O2_log	0.3136	0.002	**
O2_sat_log	0.2787	0.004	**
BOD_log	0.2811	0.005	**
TN_log	0.4170	0.001	***
NH4N_log	0.1127	0.127	
NO2N_log	0.1544	0.083	.
NO3N_log	0.0827	0.260	
SRP_log	0.1352	0.082	.
TP_log	0.2885	0.004	**

5.3 Pressure – Response Relationship

5.3.1 Pressure Index calculation

In addition to the visual inspection and the correlation analysis of typological and pressure variables to the distance matrix of the nMDS, a direct pressure-response-relationship was calculated. This was done for the correlation of the EQR of all sites and lake transects to the respective pressure variables of all sites and transects measured. This resulted in a pressure-response-matrix giving information for the change of the EQR depending on the change of the variables (Table 39). To gain even more information, this was also done for each subgroup as chosen using the nMDS above. The results reveal variable responses depending on the groups, resulting in a differentiation of global pressures and local pressures important for distinctive sites. In Addition, combined pressures were built from the CLC to increase the potential response to a valid level:

- Artificial: Discontinuous Urban Fabric + Industrial or Commercial Units + Road and Rail networks + Mineral extraction sites + Dump sites
- Agriculture: Non-irrigated arable land + Vineyards + Complex cultivation patterns + Land principally occupied by agriculture with areas of nature
- Natural: Mixed forest + Natural grassland + Moors and heathlands + Bare rocks + Sparsely vegetated areas

Table 39: Pressure-response-relationship for the selected pressure parameters.

Index	All			1_L1L3L11			2_L2L4L12L14L16			3_L6L7L8L9			4_L13L15L17			5_L05a		
	R	pval	score	R	pval	score	R	pval	score	R	pval	score	R	pval	score	R	pval	score
VegRiparian_seg (0,1,2,3)	-0,21	0,0076	**	-0,69	0,0011	**	-0,23	0,0640	.	0,27	0,0830	.	-0,28	0,2100				
VegRiparian_site (0,1,2,3)	-0,20	0,0110	*				-0,21	0,0960	.	0,35	0,0270	*	-0,37	0,0900	.			
HabAlter_seg (0,1,2,3)	-0,20	0,0130	*	-0,69	0,0011	**	-0,24	0,0510	.	0,49	0,0011	**	-0,21	0,3500				
HabAlter_site (0,1,2,3)	-0,11	0,1900					-0,22	0,0740	.	0,56	0,0001	***	-0,07	0,7400				
Toxic (0,1,2,3)	-0,04	0,6100					-0,28	0,0200	*	0,34	0,0280	*						
Water_Level_fluct (0,1,2,3)	-0,41	0,0001	****	-0,56	0,0130	*	-0,38	0,0020	**				-0,32	0,1500		0,43	0,4000	
Aquaculture (0,1,2,3)	-0,27	0,0007	***	-0,59	0,0085	**	-0,26	0,0370	*				-0,22	0,3300				
Anthr. Press. - landscape (0,1,2,3)	-0,19	0,0180	*	0,53	0,0190	*	-0,22	0,0710	.	-0,05	0,7600		-0,31	0,1700				
Anthr. Press. - physical chemistry (0,1,2,3)	-0,27	0,0008	***	-0,63	0,0086	**	-0,31	0,0100	*	0,62	0,0001	****	-0,16	0,4700				
WaterPollution (0,1)	-0,24	0,0023	**				-0,48	0,0001	****	0,16	0,3300		-0,05	0,8200				
ArtificialShadngPer (% ,0-100)	0,03	0,6800					-0,07	0,5600		0,21	0,1800		0,29	0,1900				
MigrationBarriersInArea (1,0)	0,12	0,1300		-0,53	0,0190	*	0,31	0,0100	*	0,36	0,0210	*						
TreeDistribution (0,1,2,3)	0,04	0,6600		-0,48	0,0380	*	0,11	0,3700		-0,49	0,0012	**	0,59	0,0040	**			
VegetationNaturalPer (% ,0-100)	0,05	0,5400					-0,22	0,0820	.	0,55	0,0002	***						
VegetationArtificialPer (% ,0-100)	-0,05	0,5400					0,22	0,0820	.	-0,55	0,0002	***						
AnthropogenicImpactInArea (% ,0-100)	-0,26	0,0009	***	0,53	0,0190	*	-0,33	0,0072	**	-0,09	0,5600		-0,25	0,2600		-0,43	0,4000	
Turbidity (1,2,3, clear -> strong)	-0,22	0,0066	**	-0,26	0,2900		-0,16	0,2000		0,13	0,4000		-0,05	0,8200				
Kind (1Natural/2Transitional/3HM)	-0,09	0,2900		-0,53	0,0190	*				0,54	0,0003	***						
Artificial (comb. Press. CLC % 0-100)	-0,04	0,6300					-0,14	0,2700		0,18	0,2600		0,29	0,1900				
Agriculture (comb. Press. CLC % 0-100)	-0,29	0,0002	***	0,16	0,5200		-0,23	0,0630	.	-0,29	0,0660	.	-0,21	0,3400		0,43	0,4000	
Natural (comb. Press. CLC % 0-100)	0,17	0,0410	*	0,50	0,0290	*	-0,25	0,0410	*	-0,57	0,0001	***	-0,29	0,1800				
EC_log	-0,19	0,0180	*	-0,46	0,0490	*	-0,47	0,0001	****	0,29	0,0640	.	0,14	0,5400		-0,43	0,4000	
O2_log	0,17	0,0360	*	-0,31	0,1900		0,12	0,3200		0,37	0,0160	*	0,16	0,5000		0,43	0,4000	
O2_sat_log	0,10	0,2200		-0,47	0,0420	*	0,10	0,4400		0,35	0,0230	*	0,16	0,4900		0,43	0,4000	
BOD_log	-0,22	0,0098	**	0,20	0,4100		-0,09	0,5200		-0,30	0,0530	.	-0,21	0,4100		-0,43	0,4000	
TN_log	-0,25	0,0021	**				-0,13	0,2800		-0,06	0,7100		-0,13	0,5500		-0,43	0,4000	
NH4N_log	-0,25	0,0021	**	0,53	0,0190	*	-0,15	0,2200		-0,31	0,0490	*	-0,27	0,2200		-0,43	0,4000	
NO2N_log	-0,10	0,2300					-0,08	0,5100					-0,17	0,4400				
NO3N_log	-0,02	0,7800					0,05	0,6800		0,10	0,5400		-0,28	0,2100		-0,43	0,4000	
SRP_log	-0,16	0,0480	*				-0,17	0,1700		-0,09	0,5600		0,16	0,4700		-0,43	0,4000	
TP_log	-0,27	0,0006	***				-0,38	0,0018	**	0,02	0,9000		-0,02	0,9200		-0,43	0,4000	

In the following step, most significant pressure variables were selected by expert judgement to build a pressure index. Therefore, the variables of different scale had to be adjusted to be summed up to one final value of pressure index giving a reliable information of the pressures combined existing at one specific site (or transect). For this, the following code in R was applied to meet equal scaling from 0-1 for each variable (Table 40).

Table 40: Scaling of the Pressure Index for Bulgarian lakes.

Scaling of Pressure Index (PI) to a global scale of 0-1

```
bul$PressureIndex <-
(
  bul$Migr_Barriers/max(bul$Migr_Barriers,na.rm=T)+
  bul$VegRiparian_seg/max(bul$VegRiparian_seg,na.rm=T)+
  bul$VegRiparian_site/max(bul$VegRiparian_site,na.rm=T)+
  bul$HabAlter_seg/max(bul$HabAlter_seg,na.rm=T)+
  bul$Water_level_fluct/max(bul$Water_level_fluct,na.rm=T)+
  bul$Aquaculture/max(bul$Aquaculture,na.rm=T)+
  bul`Anthropogenic pressure - landscape`/
  max(bul`Anthropogenic pressure - landscape`,na.rm=T)+
  bul`Anthropogenic pressure - physical chemistry`/
  max(bul`Anthropogenic pressure - physical chemistry`,na.rm=T)+
  bul$WaterPollution/max(bul$WaterPollution,na.rm=T)+
  bul$AnthropogenicImpactInArea/
  max(bul$AnthropogenicImpactInArea,na.rm=T)+
  bul$Turbidity/max(bul$Turbidity,na.rm=T)+
  bul$Agriculture+
  bul$EC_log/max(bul$EC_log,na.rm=T)+
  ((bul$BOD_log+(min(bul$BOD_log,na.rm=T)*-1))/max(bul$BOD_log,na.rm=T))+
  ((bul$TN_log+(min(bul$TN_log,na.rm=T)*-1))/max(bul$TN_log,na.rm=T))+
  ((bul$NH4N_log+(min(bul$NH4N_log,na.rm=T)*-1))/
  max(bul$NH4N_log,na.rm=T))+
  ((bul$SRP_log+(min(bul$SRP_log,na.rm=T)*-1))/max(bul$SRP_log,na.rm=T))+
  ((bul$TP_log+(min(bul$TP_log,na.rm=T)*-1))/max(bul$TP_log,na.rm=T))
)

bul$PressureIndex <- bul$PressureIndex/max(bul$PressureIndex,na.rm=T)
```

5.3.2 Relationship between pressure index and EQR

The Pressure Index calculated for each site (and transect) was set in correlation with the EQR values of each transect available to build a linear regression model (Figure 19, Table 41). Despite the Alpine sites with quite high EQR values would indicate a steep slope, the overall slope is flat with $-0.45x$. The R^2 is quite low (0.15) and below the threshold considered as prerequisite in the IC Guidance documents (0.25). The high variability also among lakes with comparable pressure situation is partly due to methodology and partly due to type-specific differences.

The plot in Figure 19 does not yet take into account systematic bias in this relationship in different types. It may be possible though that the biological response differs between types at the same level of pressure. In addition, even in no-pressure situation the EQR may be significantly differ between high-mountain and lowland lakes. This is the reason why type-specific classification methods are required. To cope with this problem, a linear mixed model (lmer) was developed to identify type-specific shifts in the overall regression model. This statistical tool was developed based on the experience of the first round of IC that many types lack sites in reference conditions (Mischke et al, 2016; Wolfram et al., 2016). Using linear mixed models allows calculating so-called offsets for different types (Willby et al., 2014). In the IC process, this statistical procedure was also called “continuous benchmarking” (Böhmer et al., 2011).

In brief, this method allows combining sections of different regression lines into one model. Theoretically, these differences in the regression lines may be due to different slopes or different intercepts. During the intercalibration process in other Geographical Intercalibration Groups, it was generally assumed that the regressions differed in intercept only, but not in slope. The linear mixed model was used to calculate the differences of these intercepts or offsets. The calculations were carried out in *R* with the package *lme4* (Bates et al., 2012, 2015).

The plot in Figure 19 follows the general regression model

```
lm1 <- lm (EQR ~ PI)
```

where PI is a fixed factor. Including *type* as random factor (variable intercept, fixed slope), the linear mixed model looks like:

```
lm2 <- lmer (EQR ~ PI + (1|WBType))
```

It is summarized in Table 42.

To derive the intercept-offsets of different regressions by WBType to the global linear regression, following code does the magic (Table 43):

```
coef(lm2)
```

The plot with offset-corrected EQR – *i.e.* EQR after continuous benchmarking - is shown in Figure 20. The fit for the model R^2 improves slightly from 0.15 to 0.17. The linear regression model

```
lm1 <- lm (EQR ~ PI)
```

is summarised in Table 44.

Figure 19: Correlation between the EQR and the Pressure Index.

Table 41: Linear regression model EQR vs. Pressure Index PI.

Linear regression model: EQR ~ Pressure Index PI

```
Call:
lm(formula = bul$Trans_EQR ~ bul$PressureIndex)
```

```
Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-0.52495 -0.14425  0.01742  0.16521  0.47505
```

```
Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value      Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)   0.64510   0.04817  13.391 < 0.0000000000000002 ***
bul$PressureIndex -0.45549   0.08736  -5.214   0.000000582 ***
```

```
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
Residual standard error: 0.2245 on 155 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.1492,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.1437
F-statistic: 27.19 on 1 and 155 DF,  p-value: 0.0000005824
```

Table 42: Linear mixed model with Pressure Index as fixed variable and type as random factor.

Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']

```

Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']
Formula: Trans_EQR ~ PressureIndex + (1 | WBType)
Data: bul

REML criterion at convergence: -35

Scaled residuals:
   Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.1303 -0.5647  0.1247  0.5884  2.2381

Random effects:
 Groups   Name                Variance Std.Dev.
 WBType   (Intercept)           0.02004  0.1416
 Residual                            0.03819  0.1954
Number of obs: 157, groups:  WBType, 16

Fixed effects:
              Estimate Std. Error t value
(Intercept)   0.62017    0.06674   9.292
PressureIndex -0.41179    0.10212  -4.033

Correlation of Fixed Effects:
              (Intr)
PressurIndx -0.801

```

Table 43: Offsets calculated by the Linear model, compared to the global intercept of 0.62.

Lake Type	Intercept	Offset
L01	0,93	0,31
L02	0,46	-0,16
L03	0,72	0,10
L04	0,62	0,00
L05a	0,57	-0,05
L06	0,46	-0,16
L07	0,73	0,11
L08	0,64	0,02
L09	0,67	0,05
L11	0,43	-0,19
L12	0,65	0,03
L13	0,53	-0,09
L14	0,65	0,03
L15	0,69	0,07
L16	0,53	-0,09
L17	0,64	0,02

Figure 20: Correlation between the adjusted EQR and the Pressure Index.

Table 44: Linear regression model updated EQR vs. Pressure Index PI.

Linear regression model: corrected EQR ~ Pressure Index PI

```
Call:
lm(formula = bul_adjust$Trans_EQR_adj ~ bul$PressureIndex)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-0.51008 -0.12378  0.02493  0.11733  0.43853

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  0.61936   0.03987  15.53 < 0.000000000000002 ***
bul$PressureIndex -0.41429   0.07230  -5.73  0.0000000509 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.1858 on 155 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.1748,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.1695
F-statistic: 32.83 on 1 and 155 DF,  p-value: 0.00000005087
```

5.4 Reference conditions and class boundaries for the ecological status

5.4.1 Reference values

The general procedure for defining the ecological status of lakes is the same as for rivers and as described in chapter 4.4.

As a first step we defined the following criteria for selecting reference sites:

- No HMWB
- High or good ecological status as classified used the BQE phytoplankton (see Annex 2 of the Final Report)
- Presence of reasonable macrophyte stands

Furthermore, the macrophyte species present must allow an assessment with regard to abundance and species spectrum.

Table 45. Candidate reference sites identified based on reference criteria (see text).

Lakes			
BG4ME0000NMS003	L1	Bezbojko Lake	Potential reference lake for macrophytes
BG1YN92233MS051	L2	Hristo Smirnenski Reservoir	HMWB
BG3MA06481MS0740	L3	Golyam Beglik Reservoir	HMWB
BG1WO03496MS031	L4	Rabisha Reservoir	HMWB
BG2IU200L005RP15	L5	Velyov vir Lake	Intercalibrated - not a reference lake
	L6		No reference out of 3 water bodies.
	L7		No reference out of 3 water bodies.
	L8		No reference out of 5 water bodies.
	L9		No reference out of 8 water bodies.
	L10		No reference/benchmark. There are only 2 lakes from this type in BG. They both are HMWB.
	L11		No reference out of 5 water bodies.
BG1VT00891MS051	L12	Sopot Reservoir	HMWB
	L13		No reference out of 5 water bodies.
BG1VT00325MS031	L14	Gorni Dabnik Reservoir	Not a reference lake
	L15		No reference out of 5 water bodies.
BG1OG00744MS041	L16	Srechenska Bara Reservoir	HMWB
	L17		No reference out of 5 water bodies.

In the table above it can be seen that only one reference lake would remain. On this basis a definition of reference conditions and corresponding values for biological metrics is not possible. Therefore, the class boundaries had to be defined in alternative way (see next chapter).

5.4.2 Class boundaries

For defining the class boundaries, we worked with “paired metrics”. This approach in general is described in chapter 3.5.2. of Annex 5 (Macroinvertebrates). We used the two metrics “share of reference taxa” and “share of disturbance indicating taxa”. These two groups of species correspond to the indicator species groups “A” (reference taxa) and “C” (disturbance indicators) which are defined to calculate the Bulgarian Reference Index (official Bulgarian macrophyte-based WFD-assessment system).

In the Reference Index method that point where, along the pressure gradient, disturbance indicators start to dominate reference taxa is defined to be the good-moderate (G/M) boundary. We used the whole dataset and found this point at an EQR-value of 0,46. For defining the corresponding EQR values for all types we used the type specific offsets derived in chapter 5.3.2.

Figure 21. “Crossover” of “reference taxa” (A) and “disturbance indicators” (C).

Bad status is defined as lack of macrophytes due to anthropogenic impact. The EQR-value at the poor-bad (P/B) boundary therefore result in “0,00”.

For defining the moderate-poor (M/P) boundary we used the “equal distances approach” (for a general description see chapter 3.5.2. of Annex 5 (Benthic Invertebrates).

The H/G boundary is usually derived by defining a percentile in the reference sites as the boundary. As there was not sufficient information concerning reference conditions and corresponding EQR-values of the Bulgarian assessment system we applied the “equal distance” approach also to define the high-good (H/G) boundary. As reference value the highest possible EQR-value “1,00” was assumed. The resulting EQR-values for all types and all class boundaries can be taken from Table 46.

Table 46. Type-specific values for RI-EQR in Bulgarian lakes/reservoirs.

Lake type	G/M overall	offset	G/M type	Ref	H	G	G	M	M	P	P	B
L01	0,46	0,31	0,77	1,00	0,88		0,77		0,38		0,00	
L02	0,46	-0,16	0,30	1,00	0,65		0,30		0,15		0,00	
L03	0,46	0,10	0,56	1,00	0,78		0,56		0,28		0,00	
L04	0,46	0,00	0,46	1,00	0,73		0,46		0,23		0,00	
L05a	0,46	-0,05	0,41	1,00	0,70		0,41		0,20		0,00	
L06	0,46	-0,16	0,30	1,00	0,65		0,30		0,15		0,00	
L07	0,46	0,11	0,57	1,00	0,79		0,57		0,29		0,00	
L08	0,46	0,02	0,48	1,00	0,74		0,48		0,24		0,00	
L09	0,46	0,05	0,51	1,00	0,76		0,51		0,26		0,00	
L11	0,46	-0,19	0,27	1,00	0,64		0,27		0,14		0,00	
L12	0,46	0,03	0,49	1,00	0,75		0,49		0,25		0,00	
L13	0,46	-0,09	0,37	1,00	0,69		0,37		0,19		0,00	
L14	0,46	0,03	0,49	1,00	0,74		0,49		0,24		0,00	
L15	0,46	0,07	0,53	1,00	0,76		0,53		0,26		0,00	
L16	0,46	-0,09	0,37	1,00	0,68		0,37		0,18		0,00	
L17	0,46	0,02	0,48	1,00	0,74		0,48		0,24		0,00	

5.5 Comparison with existing boundaries

For the comparison with existing boundaries see Table 47. A recommendation for adapting boundaries was only given, if the deviation of boundary values exceeded the standard deviation (0,16) resulting from the global linear model (see Table 42). (For L10 see chapter 6.2).

Table 47: Type-specific values for RI-EQR in Bulgarian lakes/reservoirs.

Lake type	existing boundaries					calculated new boundaries						
	H	G	G	M	M	P	H	G	G	M	M	P
L01	0,80		0,53			0,27	0,88		0,77			0,38
L02	0,77		0,50			0,25	0,65		0,30			0,15
L03	0,77		0,50			0,25	0,78		0,56			0,28
L04	0,75		0,50			0,25	0,73		0,46			0,23
L05a	0,825		0,575			0,21	0,70		0,41			0,20
L06	0,59		0,33			0,11	0,65		0,30			0,15
L07	0,75		0,50			0,25	0,79		0,57			0,29
L08	0,59		0,33			0,11	0,74		0,48			0,24
L09	0,59		0,33			0,11	0,76		0,51			0,26
L11	0,75		0,49			0,23	0,64		0,27			0,14
L12	0,69		0,39			0,13	0,75		0,49			0,25
L13	0,69		0,39			0,13	0,69		0,37			0,19
L14	0,75		0,49			0,23	0,74		0,49			0,24
L15	0,75		0,49			0,23	0,76		0,53			0,26
L16	0,69		0,39			0,13	0,68		0,37			0,18
L17	0,69		0,39			0,13	0,74		0,48			0,24
Lake type	differences					recommendation						
	H	G	G	M	M		P					
L01		0,08		0,24		0,11	adapt G/M boundary -> stricter					
L02		-0,12		-0,20		-0,10	adapt G/M boundary -> less strict					
L03		0,01		0,06		0,03	keep existing boundaries					
L04		-0,02		-0,04		-0,02	keep existing boundaries					
L05a		-0,12		-0,17		-0,01	keep existing boundaries; intercalibr.					
L06		0,06		-0,03		0,04	keep existing boundaries					
L07		0,04		0,07		0,04	keep existing boundaries					
L08		0,15		0,15		0,13	keep existing boundaries					
L09		0,17		0,18		0,15	adapt H/G and G/M bound. -> stricter					
L11		-0,11		-0,22		-0,09	adapt G/M boundary -> less strict					
L12		0,06		0,10		0,12	keep existing boundaries					
L13		0,00		-0,02		0,06	keep existing boundaries					
L14		-0,01		0,00		0,01	keep existing boundaries					
L15		0,01		0,04		0,03	keep existing boundaries					
L16		-0,01		-0,02		0,05	keep existing boundaries					
L17		0,05		0,09		0,11	keep existing boundaries					

6 Transitional surface water bodies

6.1 Rivers

Transitional rivers are pooled in the river type R16. This type is treated with a separate indicator list and specified class boundaries. Accordingly, for this type no separate macrophyte-based assessment system had to be designed.

Table 48. Adapted list of indicators for the river type R16. (Orange markers indicate a change or new assignment to an indicator group).

Taxon	R10/R11/R16
<i>Agrostis gigantea</i> Roth	B
<i>Agrostis stolonifera</i> L.	B
<i>Alisma lanceolatum</i> With.	B
<i>Amblystegium serpens</i> (Hedw.) Schimp.	B
<i>Angelica sylvestris</i> L.	B
<i>Apium nodiflorum</i> (L.) Lag.	B
<i>Apium repens</i> (Jacq.) Lag.	B
<i>Azolla filiculoides</i> Lam.	B
<i>Berula erecta</i> (Huds.) Coville	A
<i>Brachythecium rivulare</i> Schimp.	A
<i>Bryum turbinatum</i> (Hedw.) Turner	B
<i>Butomus umbellatus</i> L.	B
<i>Calliergon cordifolium</i> (Hedw.) Kindb.	B
<i>Calliergon giganteum</i> (Schimp.) Lindb.	A
<i>Callitriche cophocarpa</i> Sendtn.	B
<i>Callitriche platycarpa</i> Kütz.	A
<i>Callitriche stagnalis</i> Scop.	A
<i>Ceratophyllum demersum</i> L.	C
<i>Ceratophyllum submersum</i> L.	C
<i>Chara</i> spp.	A
<i>Chiloscyphus</i> Corda spp. (<i>C. pallescens</i> ; <i>C. polyanthos</i>)	A
<i>Cinclidotus aquaticus</i> (Hedw.) Bruch & Schimp.	B
<i>Cinclidotus fontinaloides</i> (Hedw.) P. Beauv.	A
<i>Cyperus fuscus</i> L.	B
<i>Cyperus longus</i> L.	B
<i>Conocephalum conicum</i> (L.) Dumort.	B
<i>Cratoneuron filicinum</i> (Hedw.) Spruce	A
<i>Dichodontium pellucidum</i> (Hedw.) Schimp.	A
<i>Drepanocladus aduncus</i> (Hedw.) Warnst.	A

<i>Drepanocladus sendtneri</i> (Schimp.) Warnst.	A
<i>Eleocharis acicularis</i> (L.) Roem. & Schult.	A
<i>Elodea canadensis</i> Michx.	B
<i>Elodea nuttallii</i> (Planch.) H. St. John	B
<i>Equisetum fluviatile</i> L.	A
<i>Fissidens adianthoides</i> Hedw.	B
<i>Fissidens crassipes</i> Wilson ex Bruch & Schimp.	A
<i>Fissidens fontanus</i> (Bach.Pyl.) Steud.	B
<i>Fissidens pusillus</i> (Wilson) Milde	B
<i>Fissidens rivularis</i> (Spruce) Schimp.	A
<i>Fontinalis antipyretica</i> Hedw.	A
<i>Fontinalis hypnoides</i> C. Hartm.	A
<i>Galium palustre</i> L.	B
<i>Glyceria fluitans</i> (L.) R. Br.	B
<i>Glyceria maxima</i> (Hartm.) Holmb.	B
<i>Groenlandia densa</i> (L.) Fourr.	A
<i>Hippuris vulgaris</i> L.	A
<i>Hydrocharis morsus-ranae</i> L.	B
<i>Hygroamblystegium fluviatile</i> (Hedw.) Loeske	A
<i>Hygroamblystegium humile</i> (P.Beauv.) Vanderp. et al.	B
<i>Hygroamblystegium tenax</i> (Hedw.) Jenn.	A
<i>Hygroamblystegium varium</i> (Hedw.) Mönk.	B
<i>Hygrohypnum luridum</i> (Hedw.) Jenn.	A
<i>Juncus articulatus</i> L.	B
<i>Juncus effusus</i> L.	B
<i>Lemna gibba</i> L.	C
<i>Lemna minor</i> L.	B
<i>Lemna trisulca</i> L.	B
<i>Leptodictyum riparium</i> (Hedw.) Warnst.	B
<i>Leskea polycarpa</i> Hedw.	B
<i>Lythrum salicaria</i> L.	B
<i>Lunularia cruciata</i> (L.) Lindb.	B
<i>Marchantia polymorpha</i> L.	B
<i>Marsupella emarginata</i> (Ehrh.) Dumort.	A
<i>Mentha aquatica</i> L.	B
<i>Myosotis scorpioides</i> L.	B
<i>Myriophyllum spicatum</i> L.	B
<i>Myriophyllum verticillatum</i> L.	B

<i>Najas marina</i> L.	A
<i>Najas minor</i> All.	A
<i>Nardia compressa</i> (Hook.) Gray	A
<i>Nasturtium officinale</i> R.Br.	A
<i>Nuphar lutea</i> Sm.	A
<i>Nymphaea alba</i> L.	A
<i>Nymphoides peltata</i> (S.G.Gmel.) Kuntze	A
<i>Oenanthe aquatica</i> (L.) Poir.	
<i>Palustriella</i> spp. (<i>P. commutata</i> , <i>P. decipiens</i>)	A
<i>Paspalum paspalodes</i> (Michx.) Scribn.	C
<i>Phalaris arundinacea</i> L.	B
<i>Platyhypnidium riparioides</i> (Hedw.) Dixon	A
<i>Polygonum amphibium</i> L.	A
<i>Polygonum hydropiper</i> L.	A
<i>Polygonum mite</i> Schrank	B
<i>Potamogeton acutifolius</i> Link	A
<i>Potamogeton berchtoldii</i> Fieber	C
<i>Potamogeton crispus</i> L.	C
<i>Potamogeton friesii</i> Rupr.	C
<i>Potamogeton gramineus</i> L.	A
<i>Potamogeton lucens</i> L.	A
<i>Potamogeton natans</i> L.	B
<i>Potamogeton natans x nodosus</i>	B
<i>Potamogeton nodosus</i> Poir.	B
<i>Potamogeton pectinatus</i> L.	C
<i>Potamogeton perfoliatus</i> L.	A
<i>Potamogeton polygonifolius</i> Pourr.	A
<i>Potamogeton praelongus</i> Wulfen	A
<i>Potamogeton pusillus</i> L.	C
<i>Potamogeton trichoides</i> Cham. & Schltdl.	C
<i>Racomitrium aciculare</i> (Hedw.) Brid.	A
<i>Ranunculus flammula</i> L.	A
<i>Ranunculus penicillatus</i> (Dumort.) Bab.	B
<i>Ranunculus repens</i> L.	B
<i>Ranunculus trichophyllus</i> Chaix	B
<i>Riccia fluitans</i> L.	A
<i>Ricciocarpos natans</i> (L.) Corda	C
<i>Ruppia maritima</i> L.	A

<i>Sagittaria sagittifolia</i> L.	B
<i>Scapania undulata</i> (L.) Dumort.	A
<i>Schistidium rivulare</i> (Brid.) Podp.	A
<i>Scirpus lacustris</i> L.	B
<i>Sciuro-hypnum plumosum</i> (Hedw.) Ignatov & Huttunen	A
<i>Sparganium emersum</i> Rehmman	B
<i>Sparganium erectum</i> L.	B
<i>Sparganium minimum</i> Wallr.	A
<i>Sphagnum</i> L. spp.	A
<i>Spirodela polyrhiza</i> (L.) Schleid.	C
<i>Stratiotes aloides</i> L.	A
<i>Trapa natans</i> L.	C
<i>Utricularia vulgaris</i> L.	A
<i>Veronica anagallis-aquatica</i> L.	B
<i>Veronica beccabunga</i> L.	B
<i>Warnstorfia fluitans</i> (Hedw.) Loeske	A
<i>Zannichellia palustris</i> L.	C

6.2 Lakes

L10

Only two water bodies in Bulgaria belong to the lake type L10: Pomorie and Atanasovsko lakes. Both oligohaline lakes are shallow and HMWB (for salt and lye extraction). Salinity is a leading factor in the state of the water bodies and is directly related to the stability of the aquatic ecosystem.

In total 27 transects were studied (14 in Atanasovsko and 13 in Pomorie). The lakes are dominated by helophyte *Phragmites australis* in conditions similar to marsh habitat (up 10 cm water level). The only hydrophyte species recorded is *Ruppia maritima* (at 60% of the transects) with highly variable abundance (between 1 and 4).

Based on these data and data from a previous 5-years project (LIFE11 NAT/BG/000262) it could be concluded that except *Ruppia maritima* there is a lack of submerged and floating aquatic plants due to the specific lake type conditions. Namely, high summer temperatures, dissolved oxygen limitation and extreme turbidity were recognized as main barriers for macrophyte development (Gecheva et al., 2017). It should be underlined that *Ruppia* responds to both, eutrophication and general degradation such as hydro-morphological changes and loss of habitat.

On this basis a new approach for a separate assessment system for the lake type L10 is proposed (Gecheva, 2021):

Based on the above *Ruppia* development with alternative metrics, as density and cover of the populations, should be monitored. The following evaluation metrics can be tested. It should be emphasized that these metrics could be reported individually, but the final score should be a combination of their values.

(i) After a precise mapping of the *Ruppia* developing in the lakes, any further loss of species can be reported as a result of changes in environmental conditions and, accordingly, reflect a deviation from the reference conditions. Conversely, any improvement in the ecological potential will be accompanied by an increase in the taxa present.

(ii) Density of *Ruppia* cover (presented as a percentage coverage per year)

Sampling sites with a size of 50/50 cm (= 0.25 m²) can be used. The number of sites (squares) should be in accordance with the *Ruppia* covered area, but should be approximately 3.

(iii) *Ruppia* cover (as a percentage of increase/decrease of the total colonized area)

This metric is likely to require a minimum of 5 years (Duarte & Kirkman, 2001), provided there are no abrupt changes in lagoon conditions.

Table 49 below provides prognosed description of *Ruppia* populations and proposed class boundaries (Gecheva, 2021).

Table 49: Characteristics of aquatic macrophyte communities according to ecological status (following Practitioners Guide to the Intertidal Seagrass tool Version 10. 061212).

ecological potential	description	boundary
maximum	There is no loss of species compared to previous years. There is no reduction in projective coverage. There is no decrease in the area of <i>Ruppia</i> cover.	0.8
good	There is no loss of species compared to previous years. Overgrowth area: <30% deviation from those described so far (i.e., within the range of natural variability). Overgrowth coverage: <30% compared to the highest recorded so far.	0.6
moderate	Overgrowth area:> 30% deviation from those described so far (i.e., beyond natural variability). Overgrowth coverage: > 30% deviation from the highest value described so far. These processes are still reversible, but require a recovery period of an average of 5 years.	0.4
poor	Largely destroyed overgrowth area and coverage: >50% deviation from those described so far.	0.2
bad	Completely absent <i>Ruppia</i> beds.	0

The ideal ecological conditions for the development of rupee are not entirely clear, so the lack of their communities in habitats that are suitable is still inexplicable (Krause-Jensen et al., 2003). In this sense, the absence of their communities does not necessarily have to be linked to bad ecological status, except in cases where there is historical evidence of the existence of such communities in previous years.

The scheme shown above should be considered preliminary. At present an assessment of lake type L10 is not possible on the basis of the existing data and further fieldwork is necessary.

7 Ecological potential of heavily modified water bodies

Annex 1 of the Final Report is a general document on ecological potential (thereafter named GD-EP) and describes the principle of ecological potential (EP) classification as defined in the CIS Guidance No 37. Furthermore, background and theoretical options for boundary setting for HMWB are outlined in Chapter 3.8. Annex 5 (Benthic Invertebrates).

Concerning the BQE macrophytes it could be shown that reaching a “good ecological status” principally should be possible in most HMWB-rivers and -lakes investigated up to now. For this reason, in the existing assessment system (Reference-Index, RI-BG, Gecheva et al., 2013) nor separate indicator lists nor separate class boundaries were defined. Accordingly, even in this study it was decided to adopt the boundary between “good” and “moderate ecological status” for heavily modified rivers and lakes as boundary between “good and higher ecological potential” and “moderate or worse ecological potential”. An accordance with the proposal given in 3.8.4. Annex 5 (Benthic Invertebrates) we will give the following recommendation:

- For types or single HMWB, where achieving a “good ecological status” is possible, the ecological potential as assessed by the BQE macrophytes should be defined in the same way as the “ecological status”.

For other HMWB-rivers and -lakes, which will be investigated in future and which cannot reach a good ecological status due to the anthropogenous modifications, we would recommend to follow the pragmatic approach given in chapter 3.8.4. Annex 5 (Benthic Invertebrates):

- For types or single HMWB, where achieving “good ecological status” is not possible, the class-boundaries of the “ecological potential” for the Reference Index (RI-BG) shall be defined 1 step (half of the respective class-width) lower as for “ecological status”.

Example for the proposed pragmatic approach in case a good ecological status is not achievable, Lake type L13:

Natural Water Bodies (Example L13)					
Ecological Status	High	Good	Moderate	Poor	Bad
Class boundaries	0,69	0,37	0,19	0,00	
Heavily Modified Water Bodies (L13) in case good ecological status is not achievable					
Ecological Potential		GEP and better	Moderate	Poor	Bad
Class boundaries		0,28	0,10	0,00	

8 Conclusion

The validation of the typology and classification system in Bulgaria for assessment of the ecological status of surface water bodies of categories “river”, “lake” and “transitional waters” was successful. For rivers the existing typology was verified and for lakes it has been adapted based on statistical analysis. The assignment of ecological boundaries was also successful after the data set has been iteratively updated and the method of “continuous benchmarking” was applied. Transitional waters were hard to analyse as there were too few sites and observations of different macrophytes to build a unique typology. Therefore, this typological rating for lake type L10 relies on expert judgement.

Although the data set appears large at first glance, the many different groups at the end result in only a few sites that can be used for classification. In addition, no macrophytes were found at multiple sites, so they could not be considered further. It was particularly unfortunate that essential moss species were not collected due to untrained teams, resulting in an incomplete representation of species composition of rivers. This made a confidence-based assessment of the sites difficult.

The existing assessment system could be confirmed for natural rivers and natural lakes, as well as for artificial and transitional water bodies. Only minor changes in some class boundaries are recommended. For transitional rivers, a specific indicator list could be elaborated, and for hyperhaline lakes a specified new assessment system is proposed.

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Annex Rivers – Sites, Metrics (RI), EQR and nEQR

MonitoringSiteCode	WBType	WBName	SiteName	SWB Code	RI	EQR	nEQR
BG1DJ00042MS040_1	R09	Chairluk River	r. Chairluk at v. Cherkovna	BG1DJ149R1002	-30.00	0.35	0.39
BG1DJ00042MS040_2	R09	Tsartsar	r. Tsaratsar near the v. Golyama Voda	BG1DJ149R1002	-30.00	0.35	0.39
BG1DJ00043MS020	R09	Tsartsar	r. Tsaratsar downstream confluence of r. Voyka at v. Malak Porovets	BG1DJ149R1002	0.00	0.50	0.48
BG1DJ00096MS1040	R09	Senkyovitsa	r. Senkyovitsa at v. Golyama voda	BG1DJ109R001	-6.45	0.47	0.46
BG1DJ00989MS1023	R09	Suha River	r. Suha downstream Odrintsi Dam	BG1DJ900R1011	-53.13	0.23	0.40
BG1DJ09942MS090	R09	Dobrichka River	r. Dobrichka at v. Rosenovo	BG1DJ200R013	-55.13	0.22	0.39
BG1DJ99499MS070	R09	Suha River	r. Suha at v. Novo Botevo	BG1DJ900R1011	-30.34	0.35	0.49
BG1IS00061MS150	R04	Lesnovska River	Lesnovska River. before inflow into Iskar River	BG1IS600R1016	-100.00	0.00	0.20
BG1IS00416MS049	R15	Zlatna Panega River	Springs of Zlatna River	BG1IS100R1024	-75.00	0.13	0.30
BG1IS04229MS1290	R04	Bebresh River	Bebresh River in Skravena village (after the low bridge)	BG1IS200R1342	88.90	0.94	0.95
BG1OG02431MS023	R08	Ribene River	Ribene River. after Lesura village	BG1OG400R1219	-20.00	0.40	0.60
BG1OS00611MS040	R08	Shavarna River	Shavarna River. before inflow into Osam River	BG1OS600R1005	-19.66	0.40	0.60
BG1OS07112MS100	R15	Maarata River	Karst Spring of Maarata - Krushina	BG1OS700R1011	-30.00	0.35	0.55
BG1RL00231MS050	R08	Cherni Lom River	Cherni Lom River. before inflow with Banski Lom River near Ostritsa village	BG1RL200R1007	-20.00	0.40	0.60
BG1RL09391MS100	R07	Beli Lom River	Beli Lom River. after Razgrad	BG1RL900R1012	-20.00	0.40	0.60
BG1VT00011MS010	R07	Vit River	Vit River. after Gulyantsi	BG1VT100R009	-63.92	0.18	0.47
BG1VT00015MS020	R07	Vit River	Vit River. after Dolna Mitropoliya. near Bivolare village. 100m after the bridge along the flow	BG1VT100R009	-58.55	0.21	0.51
BG1WO01621MS1100	R08	Nechenska Bara River	Nechenska Bara River. before inflow into Lom River. bridge between Brusartsi and Kriva Bara village	BG1WO600R1014	-51.43	0.24	0.56
BG1YN00059MS130	R07	Yantra River	Yantra River. near Dragano village - after inflow of Lefedzha River	BG1YN307R1127	-55.32	0.22	0.53
BG1YN00061MS140	R07	Lefedzha River	Lefedzha River. Briagovitsa village - before inflow into Yantra River	BG1YN600R1134	-36.47	0.32	0.63
BG2DO00831MS001	R11	Batova River	r. Batova – delta	BG2DO800R001	55.67	0.78	0.88
BG2IU00081MS254	R16	Lisovo Dere River	Lisovo Dere River (Izgrevsko Dere) - estuary. Tsarevo	BG2IU800R1115	-62.22	0.19	0.48
BG2IU00291MS003	R11		r. Ropotamo – v. Veselie downstream r. Mehmechkyoska		-5.66	0.47	0.71
BG2IU200R005RP14	R16	Ropotamo River	Ropotamo River in MR "Veliov Vir"	BG2IU200R1005	30.34	0.65	0.81
BG2IU76411MS410	R11	Karaagach River	r. Karaagach – v. Fazanovo	BG2IU600R1213	-10.26	0.45	0.63
BG2KA00043MS301	R10	Kamchiya River	Kamchiya River - Tsonevo village - Velichkovo village. after Luda Kamchiya River	BG2KA130R1002	-6.25	0.47	0.65
BG2KA00119MS001	R10	Kamchiya River	Kamchiya River - "Poda" area	BG2KA130R1102	-36.00	0.32	0.52

BG2KA00195MS002	R10	Kamchiya River	Kamchiya River - Grozdiovo village	BG2KA130R1002	-20.45	0.40	0.60
BG2KA04173MS233	R10	Kamchiya River	Kamchiya River - Venelin village	BG2KA130R1102	-54.10	0.23	0.43
BG2KA09153MS208	R04	Kamchiya River	Kamchiya River – before V.Preslav	BG2KA900R1019	-58.62	0.21	0.38
BG2KA41913MS302	R10	Kamchiya River	Kamchiya River - Dabravino village	BG2KA130R1102	-36.54	0.32	0.48
BG2KA47522MS452	R04	Kamchiya River	Kamchiya River - between Radko Dimitriev village and Salamanovo village	BG2KA578R1003	-87.20	0.06	0.26
BG2KA900R1020	R04	Kamchiya River	Kamchiya River. after Ticha Reservoir near V. Preslav	BG2KA900R1020	-25.00	0.38	0.53
BG2MA00221MS249	R11	Izvorska River	r. Izvorska – upstream delta between Dimchevo and Tvarditsa	BG2MA200R003	0.00	0.50	0.67
BG2MA00713MS004	R11		r. Sredetska – downstream the city of Sredets. Avramov bridge		-38.71	0.31	0.51
BG2MA06931MS370	R11	Sredetska River	r. Sredetska – bridge to v.Valchanovo	BG2MA900R1020	0.00	0.50	0.67
BG2MA66131MS364	R11	Rusocastrenska River	r. Rusokastrenska – v. Trastikovo	BG2MA600R005	1.79	0.51	0.67
BG2PR00033MS003	R11	Provadiyska River	r. Provadiyska – v. Sindel	BG2PR345R1207	-29.11	0.35	0.55
BG2PR00511MS005	R11	Provadiyska River	r. Provadiyska – downstream the city of Provadia/after Provadsol	BG2PR345R1107	18.03	0.59	0.73
BG2PR02517MS278	R11	Provadiyska River	r. Provadiyska – upstream the city of Provadia	BG2PR500R006	-10.00	0.45	0.63
BG2PR211MS002	R15	Devnenska River	Devnenska River - estuary	BG2PR210R1005	-98.72	0.01	0.21
BG2RE00219MS255	R11	Silistar River	r. Silistar – upstream delta. bridge on the Rezovo - Sinemorets road	BG2RE200R1301	27.06	0.64	0.73
BG2RE00219MS497	R16	Silistar River	Silistar River - before inflow into Black Sea (estuary)	BG2RE200R1201	-28.36	0.36	0.51
BG2RE92529MS496	R16	Butamiyata River	Butamiyata River- estuary	BG2RE200R1101	-56.45	0.22	0.39
BG2SE00061MS005	R11		r. Hadjiiska – v. Tankovo		-39.38	0.30	0.46
BG2SE00219MS228	R16	Fandakliyska River	Fandakliyska River - estuary	BG2SE200R1101	-62.79	0.19	0.36
BG2SE09613MS015	R11	Aytoska River	r. Aytoska – downstream the city of Kameno	BG2SE900R036	23.55	0.62	0.64
BG2SE400R006RP08	R11	Dvoinitsa River	r. Dvoinitsa. before the village of Popovich	BG2SE400R1006	2.22	0.51	0.55
BG2SE81MS008	R16	Aheloy River	Aheloy River - Camping Aheloy	BG2SE800R020	0.00	0.50	0.54
BG2VE08179MS419	R10	Veleka River	Veleka River - Brodilovo village	BG2VE106R1301	47.37	0.74	0.75
BG2VE111MS001	R16	Veleka River	Veleka River – Sinemorets village	BG2VE106R1801	-21.37	0.39	0.47
BG3MA00041MS0400	R13	Stryama River	r. Stryama. s. Manole	BG3MA400R076	-71.92	0.14	0.30
BG3MA00055MS0670	R12	Maritsa River	Maritsa River. Plovdiv. walkways. HMS 304	BG3MA500R217	19.42	0.60	0.62
BG3MA00094MS1462	R03	Yadenitsa River	Yadenitsa River - after Yundola	BG3MA900R200	0.00	0.50	0.54
BG3MA00229MS0132	R13	Ovcharitsa River	Ovcharitsa River - Prohoro village -ford of black road before the village	BG3MA200R026	-7.48	0.46	0.52
BG3MA00371MS0320	R12	Maritsa River	Maritsa River. bridge for Parvomay. after the bridge of Parvomay. left shore before Mechka River	BG3MA350R211	-31.43	0.34	0.44
BG3MA00421MS0403	R13	Stryama River	Stryama River - Razhevo Konare village	BG3MA400R214	-60.95	0.20	0.33

BG3MA00471MS0490	R05	Stryama River	Stryama River. Banya vil- lage	BG3MA400R214	-55.83	0.22	0.35
BG3MA00523MS0594	R03	Chepelarska Ri- ver	Chepelarska River. after Bachkovo village. between the two tunnels	BG3MA500R104	0.00	0.50	0.54
BG3MA00583MS0698	R13	Potoka River	Potoka River before Saedi- nenie	BG3MA500R129	15.69	0.58	0.60
BG3MA00711MS0848	R12	Maritsa River	Maritsa River. before Vacha River. landfill of Plovdiv	BG3MA700R143	-82.79	0.09	0.28
BG3MA00719MS0850	R12	Maritsa River	Maritsa River. Stamboliyski - the bridge	BG3MA700R143	-20.00	0.40	0.57
BG3MA00731MS0902	R12	Maritsa River	Maritsa River. Govedare vil- lage	BG3MA700R143	-42.19	0.29	0.47
BG3MA00739MS0910	R12	Maritsa River	Maritsa River Ognyanovo village. after Luda Yana River	BG3MA700R143	-20.00	0.40	0.57
BG3MA00861MS1172	R05	Bunovshitsa River	Bunovshitsa River. after Smolska River inflow. be- fore estuary	BG3MA800R166	-100.00	0.00	0.20
BG3MA00995MS1571	R03	Maritsa River	Maritsa River before the town of Dolna Banya	BG3MA900R230	45.00	0.73	0.81
BG3MA00997MS1580	R03	Maritsa River	Maritsa River near the vil- lage of Raduil	BG3MA900R230	83.50	0.92	0.94
BG3MA04991MS0553	R05	Stryama River	Stryama River. before Slat- ina village	BG3MA400R214	50.00	0.75	0.83
BG3MA05213MS0570	R05	Chepelarska Ri- ver	Chepelarska River. the bridge of Kemera	BG3MA500R103	0.00	0.50	0.65
BG3TU00013MS0010	R12	Tundzha River	Tundzha River. Srem village. 200 m after the bridge for Srem village. right shore	BG3TU100R002	-32.98	0.34	0.53
BG3TU00539MS0061	R12	Tundzha River	Tundzha River. bridge in El- hovo	BG3TU135R005	-12.90	0.44	0.62
BG3TU00719MS0160	R12	Tundzha River	Tundzha River. Samuilovo village. after Asenovska River. before the bridge. left shore	BG3TU570R067	-17.14	0.41	0.60
BG3TU00723MS0171	R03	Asenovska Ri- ver	Asenovska River - before Sliven. after plashes	BG3TU700R029	-100.00	0.00	0.20
BG3TU00937MS0290	R05	Tundzha River	Tundzha River. Yagoda vil- lage. bridge on road Stara Zagora-Kazanlak	BG3TU900R042	-100.00	0.00	0.20
BG4ME00044MS403	R13	Matnitsa River	Matnitsa River below Pet- relik village	BG4ME400R112	-20.00	0.40	0.59
BG4ME00481MS140	R15	Iztok River	Iztok River. before inflowing in Mesta River	BG4ME800R084	-33.73	0.33	0.52
BG4ME04792MS401	R05	Ruzhdavitsa Ri- ver	Ruzhdavitsa River near Dobrinishte	BG4ME700R091	0.00	0.50	0.74
BG4ME47319MS409	R05	Mesta River	Mesta River. second bridge near Gospodnitsi village	BG4ME700R090	-3.57	0.48	0.73
BG4ME47389MS403	R01	Retidzhe River	Retidzhe River. before HPP 1	BG4ME700R096	0.00	0.50	0.74
BG4ME47521MS401	R03	Bezbozhka Ri- ver	Bezbozhka River. before es- tuary. bridge on the road for Gotse Delchev	BG4ME700R094	0.00	0.50	0.74
BG4ST00622MS900	R15	Petrovska River	Petrovska River. before estuary	BG4ST200R077	-30.00	0.35	0.65
BG4ST00631MS320	R05	Struma River	Struma River near the boarder (bridge for Toplnitsa village)	BG4ST300R073	-100.00	0.00	0.20
BG4ST00632MS601	R13	Mochura River	Mochura River. Stefanov peak	BG4ST300R1074	-20.00	0.40	0.63
BG4ST06569MS402	R01	Blagoevgradska Bistritsa River	Blagoevgradska Bistritsa River. after Bodrost area. before Slavova River	BG4ST500R1045	0.00	0.50	0.69
BG4ST06582MS405	R01	Iliina River	Iliina River. before the estu- ary of Rilska River	BG4ST500R1041	0.00	0.50	0.69

BG4ST06961MS380	R13	Arkata River	Arkata River. before inflow into Struma River	BG4ST900R1009	-53.15	0.23	0.47
BG4ST65333MS403	R05	Struma River	Struma River before inflow of Belishka River (Shashka)	BG4ST500R057	-100.00	0.00	0.20
BG4ST65341MS401	R01	Vlahinska River	Vlahinska River. before Sin-anishka River inflow near Vlaha village	BG4ST500R059	0.00	0.50	0.69

nEQR calculated according to Annex 5 Benthic invertebrates.

Each class includes the lower class boundary (e.g. nEQR = 0.8 → high status).

Annex Lakes – Sites, Metrics (RI), EQR and nEQR

SiteTransect	WB-Type	name	n trans. sampled	Transect RI	Trans. EQR	Trans. nEQR	Mean RI	Mean EQR	Mean nEQR
BG1IS69539MS041_T1	L02	Ognyanovo Reservoir	5	-100.00	0.00	0.20	-87.31	0.06	0.28
BG1IS69539MS041_T2	L02	Ognyanovo Reservoir	5	-100.00	0.00	0.20	-87.31	0.06	0.28
BG1IS69539MS041_T3	L02	Ognyanovo Reservoir	5	-36.55	0.32	0.61	-87.31	0.06	0.28
BG1IS69539MS041_T5	L02	Ognyanovo Reservoir	5	-100.00	0.00	0.20	-87.31	0.06	0.28
BG1IS69539MS041_T4	L02	Ognyanovo Reservoir	5	-100.00	0.00	0.20	-87.31	0.06	0.28
BG1L04NVHM001_EEA_T2	L04	Dragoman marsh	3	-4.48	0.48	0.30	-52.19	0.24	0.41
BG1L04NVHM001_EEA_T3	L04	Dragoman marsh	3	-75.00	0.13	0.61	-52.19	0.24	0.41
BG1L04NVHM001_EEA_T1	L04	Dragoman marsh	3	-77.08	0.11	0.31	-52.19	0.24	0.41
BG1OG00739MS031_T4	L14	Ogosta Reservoir	5	-61.49	0.19	0.20	-58.35	0.21	0.37
BG1OG00739MS031_T3	L14	Ogosta Reservoir	5	-100.00	0.00	0.36	-58.35	0.21	0.37
BG1OG00739MS031_T5	L14	Ogosta Reservoir	5	-13.56	0.43	0.55	-58.35	0.21	0.37
BG1OG00744MS041_T1	L12	Srechenska Bara Reservoir	4	93.75	0.97	0.98	53.36	0.77	0.81
BG1OG00744MS041_T2	L12	Srechenska Bara Reservoir	4	86.11	0.93	0.94	53.36	0.77	0.81
BG1OG00744MS041_T4	L12	Srechenska Bara Reservoir	4	88.57	0.94	0.38	53.36	0.77	0.81
BG1OG00744MS041_T3	L12	Srechenska Bara Reservoir	4	-55.00	0.23	0.95	53.36	0.77	0.81
BG1VT00032MS041_T4	L12	Telish reservoir	4	-20.93	0.40	0.28	-36.40	0.32	0.46
BG1VT00032MS041_T1	L12	Telish reservoir	4	-79.69	0.10	0.57	-36.40	0.32	0.46
BG1VT00032MS041_T2	L12	Telish reservoir	4	-8.70	0.46	0.46	-36.40	0.32	0.46
BG1VT00032MS041_T3	L12	Telish reservoir	4	-36.27	0.32	0.52	-36.40	0.32	0.46
BG1VT00325MS031_T2	L14	Gorni Dabnik Reservoir	6	8.25	0.54	0.63	3.70	0.52	0.62
BG1VT00325MS031_T5	L14	Gorni Dabnik Reservoir	6	20.99	0.60	0.64	3.70	0.52	0.62
BG1VT00325MS031_T4	L14	Gorni Dabnik Reservoir	6	-5.97	0.47	0.61	3.70	0.52	0.62
BG1VT00325MS031_T6	L14	Gorni Dabnik Reservoir	6	-5.97	0.47	0.58	3.70	0.52	0.62
BG1VT00325MS031_T1	L14	Gorni Dabnik Reservoir	6	4.88	0.52	0.69	3.70	0.52	0.62
BG1VT00325MS031_T3	L14	Gorni Dabnik Reservoir	6	0.00	0.50	0.58	3.70	0.52	0.62
BG1VT00891MS051_T4	L12	Sopot Reservoir	6	-2.05	0.49	0.79	10.10	0.55	0.65
BG1VT00891MS051_T1	L12	Sopot Reservoir	6	47.41	0.74	0.79	10.10	0.55	0.65
BG1VT00891MS051_T6	L12	Sopot Reservoir	6	-11.84	0.44	0.61	10.10	0.55	0.65
BG1VT00891MS051_T3	L12	Sopot Reservoir	6	1.11	0.51	0.60	10.10	0.55	0.65
BG1VT00891MS051_T5	L12	Sopot Reservoir	6	-21.28	0.39	0.52	10.10	0.55	0.65
BG1VT00891MS051_T2	L12	Sopot Reservoir	6	47.27	0.74	0.56	10.10	0.55	0.65
BG1WO00814MS071_T1	L16	Rasovo reservoir	1	0.00	0.50	0.68	0.00	0.50	0.68
BG1WO03496MS031_T3	L04	Rabisha Reservoir	4	3.26	0.52	0.73	12.07	0.56	0.67
BG1WO03496MS031_T1	L04	Rabisha Reservoir	4	28.08	0.64	0.65	12.07	0.56	0.67
BG1WO03496MS031_T2	L04	Rabisha Reservoir	4	6.55	0.53	0.64	12.07	0.56	0.67
BG1WO03496MS031_T4	L04	Rabisha Reservoir	4	10.38	0.55	0.67	12.07	0.56	0.67
BG1YN04471MS031_T2	L12	Krapets Reservoir	4	-62.77	0.19	0.38	-43.07	0.28	0.43

BG1YN04471MS031_T3	L12	Krapets Reservoir	4	-19.78	0.40	0.35	-43.07	0.28	0.43
BG1YN04471MS031_T1	L12	Krapets Reservoir	4	-54.63	0.23	0.53	-43.07	0.28	0.43
BG1YN04471MS031_T4	L12	Krapets Reservoir	4	-35.09	0.32	0.46	-43.07	0.28	0.43
BG1YN06295MS180_T2	L02	Yovkovtsi Reservoir-Tail	6	-23.41	0.38	0.47	-62.91	0.19	0.45
BG1YN06295MS180_T6	L02	Yovkovtsi Reservoir-Tail	6	-53.60	0.23	0.65	-62.91	0.19	0.45
BG1YN06295MS180_T4	L02	Yovkovtsi Reservoir-Tail	6	-65.47	0.17	0.36	-62.91	0.19	0.45
BG1YN06295MS180_T1	L02	Yovkovtsi Reservoir-Tail	6	-59.25	0.20	0.43	-62.91	0.19	0.45
BG1YN06295MS180_T5	L02	Yovkovtsi Reservoir-Tail	6	-100.00	0.00	0.20	-62.91	0.19	0.45
BG1YN06295MS180_T3	L02	Yovkovtsi Reservoir-Tail	6	-75.74	0.12	0.51	-62.91	0.19	0.45
BG1YN43199MS021_T2	L14	Aleksandar Stambplyiski Reservoir	6	47.27	0.74	0.45	-3.97	0.48	0.59
BG1YN43199MS021_T4	L14	Aleksandar Stambplyiski Reservoir	6	6.85	0.53	0.80	-3.97	0.48	0.59
BG1YN43199MS021_T6	L14	Aleksandar Stambplyiski Reservoir	6	-21.05	0.39	0.61	-3.97	0.48	0.59
BG1YN43199MS021_T1	L14	Aleksandar Stambplyiski Reservoir	6	-38.83	0.31	0.64	-3.97	0.48	0.59
BG1YN43199MS021_T5	L14	Aleksandar Stambplyiski Reservoir	6	-19.15	0.40	0.53	-3.97	0.48	0.59
BG1YN43199MS021_T3	L14	Aleksandar Stambplyiski Reservoir	6	1.11	0.51	0.52	-3.97	0.48	0.59
BG1YN92233MS051_T1	L02	Hristo Smirnenski Reservoir	4	62.53	0.81	0.89	34.59	0.67	0.81
BG1YN92233MS051_T3	L02	Hristo Smirnenski Reservoir	4	-16.27	0.42	0.88	34.59	0.67	0.81
BG1YN92233MS051_T4	L02	Hristo Smirnenski Reservoir	4	32.42	0.66	0.67	34.59	0.67	0.81
BG1YN92233MS051_T2	L02	Hristo Smirnenski Reservoir	4	59.69	0.80	0.81	34.59	0.67	0.81
BG2DO10000MS007_T1	L07	Shablensko Lake	2	-41.53	0.29	0.40	-20.95	0.40	0.48
BG2DO10000MS007_T2	L07	Shablensko Lake	2	-0.36	0.50	0.55	-20.95	0.40	0.48
BG2DO10000MS483_T1	L07	Lake Ezeretsko	1	4.92	0.52	0.57	4.92	0.52	0.57
BG2IU00061MS258_T1	L08	Dyavolsko blato	4	0.00	0.50	0.62	0.00	0.50	0.62
BG2IU00061MS258_T2	L08	Dyavolsko blato	4	0.00	0.50	0.62	0.00	0.50	0.62
BG2IU00061MS258_T4	L08	Dyavolsko blato	4	0.00	0.50	0.62	0.00	0.50	0.62
BG2IU00061MS258_T3	L08	Dyavolsko blato	4	0.00	0.50	0.62	0.00	0.50	0.62
BG2IU10000MS004_T4	L08	Alepu Lake	4	-24.32	0.38	0.32	-55.39	0.22	0.39
BG2IU10000MS004_T1	L08	Alepu Lake	4	-70.33	0.15	0.32	-55.39	0.22	0.39
BG2IU10000MS004_T3	L08	Alepu Lake	4	-56.57	0.22	0.38	-55.39	0.22	0.39
BG2IU10000MS004_T2	L08	Alepu Lake	4	-70.33	0.15	0.52	-55.39	0.22	0.39
BG2IU20000MS257_T1	L08	Stamopolu	1	-100.00	0.00	0.20	-	0.00	0.20
BG2IU200L005RP15_T1	L05a	Velyov vir Lake	2	-28.80	0.36	0.55	-21.88	0.39	0.58
BG2IU200L005RP15_T2	L05a	Velyov vir Lake	2	-14.95	0.43	0.61	-21.88	0.39	0.58
BG2IU200L019RP18_T2	L05a	Arkutino Lake	4	-43.75	0.28	0.57	-39.12	0.30	0.50

BG2IU200L019RP18_T1	L05a	Arkutino Lake	4	-24.69	0.38	0.48	-39.12	0.30	0.50
BG2IU200L019RP18_T4	L05a	Arkutino Lake	4	-17.78	0.41	0.35	-39.12	0.30	0.50
BG2IU200L019RP18_T3	L05a	Arkutino Lake	4	-70.27	0.15	0.60	-39.12	0.30	0.50
BG2KA08471MS261_T3	L16	Fisek Reservoir	4	-93.10	0.03	0.50	-70.90	0.15	0.36
BG2KA08471MS261_T4	L16	Fisek Reservoir	4	-94.59	0.03	0.47	-70.90	0.15	0.36
BG2KA08471MS261_T2	L16	Fisek Reservoir	4	-50.00	0.25	0.24	-70.90	0.15	0.36
BG2KA08471MS261_T1	L16	Fisek Reservoir	4	-45.90	0.27	0.23	-70.90	0.15	0.36
BG2KA47379MS488_T2	L04	Skala 1 Reservoir	2	-27.09	0.36	0.39	-42.21	0.29	0.45
BG2KA47379MS488_T1	L04	Skala 1 Reservoir	2	-57.32	0.21	0.52	-42.21	0.29	0.45
BG2MA00019MS009_T3	L09	Mandra-East	4	0.00	0.50	0.59	0.00	0.50	0.59
BG2MA00019MS009_T4	L09	Mandra-East	4	0.00	0.50	0.59	0.00	0.50	0.59
BG2MA00019MS009_T1	L09	Mandra-East	4	0.00	0.50	0.59	0.00	0.50	0.59
BG2MA00019MS009_T2	L09	Mandra-East	4	0.00	0.50	0.59	0.00	0.50	0.59
BG2MA10000MS007_T7	L07	Mandra Reservoir	8	-3.45	0.48	0.55	-2.41	0.49	0.54
BG2MA10000MS007_T5	L07	Mandra Reservoir	8	0.00	0.50	0.55	-2.41	0.49	0.54
BG2MA10000MS007_T8	L07	Mandra Reservoir	8	-10.00	0.45	0.55	-2.41	0.49	0.54
BG2MA10000MS007_T2	L07	Mandra Reservoir	8	0.00	0.50	0.55	-2.41	0.49	0.54
BG2MA10000MS007_T3	L07	Mandra Reservoir	8	0.00	0.50	0.54	-2.41	0.49	0.54
BG2MA10000MS007_T6	L07	Mandra Reservoir	8	-3.45	0.48	0.54	-2.41	0.49	0.54
BG2MA10000MS007_T1	L07	Mandra Reservoir	8	0.00	0.50	0.51	-2.41	0.49	0.54
BG2SE08331MS028_T2	L16	Aheloy	4	-100.00	0.00	0.20	-	0.00	0.20
BG2SE90000MS022_T3	L08	Burgasko Lake-West	8	0.00	0.50	0.62	-17.81	0.39	0.53
BG2SE90000MS022_T6	L08	Burgasko Lake-West	8	-75.00	0.13	0.62	-17.81	0.39	0.53
BG2SE90000MS022_T7	L08	Burgasko Lake-West	8	-14.55	0.43	0.62	-17.81	0.39	0.53
BG2SE90000MS022_T5	L08	Burgasko Lake-West	8	-52.94	0.24	0.62	-17.81	0.39	0.53
BG2SE90000MS022_T4	L08	Burgasko Lake-West	8	0.00	0.50	0.40	-17.81	0.39	0.53
BG2SE90000MS022_T8	L08	Burgasko Lake-West	8	-33.33	0.33	0.30	-17.81	0.39	0.53
BG2SE90000MS022_T2	L08	Burgasko Lake-West	8	0.00	0.50	0.56	-17.81	0.39	0.53
BG2SE90000MS022_T1	L08	Burgasko Lake-West	8	0.00	0.50	0.48	-17.81	0.39	0.53
BG2SE90000MS024_T6	L08	Burgasko Lake-East	6	0.00	0.50	0.62	0.00	0.50	0.62
BG2SE90000MS024_T2	L08	Burgasko Lake-East	6	0.00	0.50	0.62	0.00	0.50	0.62
BG2SE90000MS024_T4	L08	Burgasko Lake-East	6	0.00	0.50	0.62	0.00	0.50	0.62
BG2SE90000MS024_T3	L08	Burgasko Lake-East	6	0.00	0.50	0.62	0.00	0.50	0.62
BG2SE90000MS024_T1	L08	Burgasko Lake-East	6	0.00	0.50	0.62	0.00	0.50	0.62
BG2SE90000MS024_T5	L08	Burgasko Lake-East	6	0.00	0.50	0.62	0.00	0.50	0.62
BG3AR00133MS0020_T4	L15	Ivaylovgrad reservoir	9	-5.56	0.47	0.56	-5.56	0.47	0.56
BG3L06MANA002_EEA_T1	L06	Krairechna martvitsa Lake near Popovitsa	1	-100.00	0.00	0.20	-	0.00	0.20
BG3L06MANA003_EEA_T2	L06	Zlato pole	2	-92.89	0.04	0.42	-79.65	0.10	0.34
BG3L06MANA003_EEA_T1	L06	Zlato pole	2	-66.40	0.17	0.25	-79.65	0.10	0.34
BG3MA00225MS0120_T2	L15	Ovcharitsa Reservoir	6	-11.43	0.44	0.52	-9.29	0.45	0.54
BG3MA00225MS0120_T1	L15	Ovcharitsa Reservoir	6	-16.19	0.42	0.54	-9.29	0.45	0.54
BG3MA00225MS0120_T3	L15	Ovcharitsa Reservoir	6	-0.24	0.50	0.58	-9.29	0.45	0.54

BG3MA00324MS1239_T3	L13	Garvanovo Reservoir	4	-66.67	0.17	0.47	-64.17	0.18	0.39
BG3MA00324MS1239_T4	L13	Garvanovo Reservoir	4	-90.00	0.05	0.47	-64.17	0.18	0.39
BG3MA00324MS1239_T2	L13	Garvanovo Reservoir	4	-50.00	0.25	0.38	-64.17	0.18	0.39
BG3MA00324MS1239_T1	L13	Garvanovo Reservoir	4	-50.00	0.25	0.25	-64.17	0.18	0.39
BG3MA00338MS7269_T1	L17	Chirpan Reservoir	3	-50.00	0.25	0.41	-50.86	0.25	0.40
BG3MA00338MS7269_T2	L17	Chirpan Reservoir	3	-51.72	0.24	0.40	-50.86	0.25	0.40
BG3MA02191MS0116_T2	L15	Rozov Kladenets Reservoir	5	0.00	0.50	0.58	-25.00	0.38	0.49
BG3MA02191MS0116_T5	L15	Rozov Kladenets Reservoir	5	-100.00	0.00	0.58	-25.00	0.38	0.49
BG3MA02191MS0116_T4	L15	Rozov Kladenets Reservoir	5	0.00	0.50	0.58	-25.00	0.38	0.49
BG3MA02191MS0116_T1	L15	Rozov Kladenets Reservoir	5	0.00	0.50	0.20	-25.00	0.38	0.49
BG3MA06481MS0740_T1	L03	Golyam Beglik Reservoir	5	50.00	0.75	0.77	69.29	0.85	0.86
BG3MA06481MS0740_T2	L03	Golyam Beglik Reservoir	5	77.14	0.89	0.90	69.29	0.85	0.86
BG3MA06481MS0740_T5	L03	Golyam Beglik Reservoir	5	50.00	0.75	1.00	69.29	0.85	0.86
BG3MA06481MS0740_T4	L03	Golyam Beglik Reservoir	5	100.00	1.00	0.77	69.29	0.85	0.86
BG3MA18739MS0071_T1	L13	Trakiets Reservoir	5	20.24	0.60	0.74	-15.18	0.42	0.63
BG3MA18739MS0071_T5	L13	Trakiets Reservoir	5	-10.71	0.45	0.44	-15.18	0.42	0.63
BG3MA18739MS0071_T4	L13	Trakiets Reservoir	5	-55.07	0.22	0.65	-15.18	0.42	0.63
BG3MA92259MS1410_T7	L03	Batak Reservoir	8	100.00	1.00	0.59	8.95	0.54	0.59
BG3MA92259MS1410_T6	L03	Batak Reservoir	8	-5.30	0.47	0.35	8.95	0.54	0.59
BG3MA92259MS1410_T1	L03	Batak Reservoir	8	8.47	0.54	0.77	8.95	0.54	0.59
BG3MA92259MS1410_T3	L03	Batak Reservoir	8	50.00	0.75	0.20	8.95	0.54	0.59
BG3MA92259MS1410_T4	L03	Batak Reservoir	8	-100.00	0.00	0.56	8.95	0.54	0.59
BG3MA92259MS1410_T2	L03	Batak Reservoir	8	-56.67	0.22	0.54	8.95	0.54	0.59
BG3MA92259MS1410_T8	L03	Batak Reservoir	8	75.06	0.88	1.00	8.95	0.54	0.59
BG3MA92259MS1410_T5	L03	Batak Reservoir	8	0.00	0.50	0.89	8.95	0.54	0.59
BG3TU05239MS0040_T4	L13	Malko Sharkovo Reservoir	5	-35.13	0.32	0.58	-29.49	0.35	0.58
BG3TU05239MS0040_T1	L13	Malko Sharkovo Reservoir	5	-29.63	0.35	0.58	-29.49	0.35	0.58
BG3TU05239MS0040_T3	L13	Malko Sharkovo Reservoir	5	-29.63	0.35	0.58	-29.49	0.35	0.58
BG3TU05239MS0040_T5	L13	Malko Sharkovo Reservoir	5	-23.44	0.38	0.55	-29.49	0.35	0.58
BG3TU05239MS0040_T2	L13	Malko Sharkovo Reservoir	5	-29.63	0.35	0.61	-29.49	0.35	0.58
BG4L06MENA001_EEA_T1	L06	Riparian Wetlands	1	-33.78	0.33	0.62	-33.78	0.33	0.62
BG4ME0000NMS003_T1	L01	Bezbojko Lake	4	100.00	1.00	1.00	100.00	1.00	1.00
BG4ME0000NMS003_T4	L01	Bezbojko Lake	4	100.00	1.00	1.00	100.00	1.00	1.00
BG4ME0000NMS003_T2	L01	Bezbojko Lake	4	100.00	1.00	1.00	100.00	1.00	1.00
BG4ME0000NMS003_T3	L01	Bezbojko Lake	4	100.00	1.00	1.00	100.00	1.00	1.00
BG4ME00292MS905_T4	L11	Dospat Reservoir-wall	8	-88.89	0.06	0.57	-62.96	0.19	0.47
BG4ME00292MS905_T1	L11	Dospat Reservoir-wall	8	-50.00	0.25	0.57	-62.96	0.19	0.47
BG4ME00292MS905_T3	L11	Dospat Reservoir-wall	8	-50.00	0.25	0.28	-62.96	0.19	0.47
BG4ST00691MS805_T2	L04	Choklyovo blato	4	0.00	0.50	0.56	-33.78	0.33	0.49

BG4ST00691MS805_T3	L04	Choklyovo blato	4	-83.16	0.08	0.63	-33.78	0.33	0.49
BG4ST00691MS805_T1	L04	Choklyovo blato	4	-18.18	0.41	0.27	-33.78	0.33	0.49
L14_Gorni Dab-nik_tail_MPH_18072020_T1	L14	Gorni Dabnik-tail	2	-0.65	0.50	0.61	0.00	0.00	0.20
L14_Gorni Dab-nik_tail_MPH_18072020_T2	L14	Gorni Dabnik-tail	2	-10.00	0.45	0.57	0.00	0.00	0.20
L14_Ogosta-tail_MPH_15072020_T1	L14	Ogosta-tail	1	-11.11	0.44	0.56	0.00	0.00	0.20

nEQR calculated according to Annex 5 Benthic invertebrates.

Each class includes the lower class boundary (e.g. nEQR = 0.8 → high status).